

Automated Shunting in Rail Freight Yards

Master Thesis

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Dipl.-Ing. Celestino Sánchez Martín

E-Mail-Adresse: celestinosanchez@posteo.net

Matr.-Nr.: 349905

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am FG Schienenfahrwege und Bahnbetrieb der TU Berlin

Betreuer: Philipp Schneider, M.Sc.

Dr.-Ing. Johannes Friedrich

Eidesstattliche Erklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig und eigenhändig sowie ohne unerlaubte fremde Hilfe und ausschließlich unter Verwendung der aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe.

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Aufgabenstellung

Traditionally, shunting has been an important part of rail operations. Until today, this process has required a large workforce as well as careful resources planning. These issues, along with the economic pressure to reduce costs, have pushed the rail system to search for alternatives or improvements. Main options consisted traditionally in either avoiding shunting by for example, using multiple unit configurations for passenger trains or facilitating the process by means of technological innovations by for example developing automatic couplers.

This work will focus on technological innovations and will explore the possibilities offered by the automation. To this end, the first part of the work will review the latest innovations in this field, concentrating on freight yard facilities. This will include both on-field experiences and state-of-the-art research at the European level as well as a selection of relevant experiences around the world. To this end, a description of the different steps of the non-automated shunting process will be described. In addition, the innovations will be grouped according to the different steps within the shunting process.

The second part will consist of developing an application-case for the automatic shunting of a wagon within a marshalling yard from the reception until the departure. The current (non-automated) shunting process will be compared with an automated scenario, which includes (at least) technical and process-related issues. Particular attention will be given to the possibilities offered by the ETCS for the shunting process. Additionally, both scenarios will be evaluated and compared using a selection of indicators (e.g. process times, assets), emphasizing economic effects.

Both parts will be investigated by means of a profound literature research and interviews with relevant stakeholders from the railway sector. The work will be written in English and will include an abstract in German.

Abstract

This thesis examines the status of automation in freight yards and assesses the time savings derived from increasing the automation level. To this end, the current shunting processes performed in a hump marshalling yard are described. A scale of automation was defined and a survey was then conducted of the most relevant innovations in the field of automation shunting. The technological maturity of these innovations was assessed.

With the results, three scenarios having different levels of automation were defined. The shunting-process times for each of them were evaluated using a model freight train. The analysis showed that implementing the existing commercial technology would lead to time savings (without considering idle times) of up to 36% in relation to the current practices. The time savings could increase to 72% if technologies that are not yet on the market become available.

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Kurzfassung

Die vorliegende Arbeit zielt auf die Entwicklung eines besseren Verständnisses des Status der Automatisierung in Güterbahnhöfen ab und bewertet die Zeitersparnis, die sich aus der Erhöhung ihres Automatisierungsgrades ergibt. Zu diesem Zweck werden die aktuellen Rangierprozesse auf einem Rangierbahnhof beschrieben. Nach der Definition einer Automatisierungsskala wird eine Übersicht über die wichtigsten Innovationen im Bereich des automatisierten Rangierens durchgeführt und die technologische Reife dieser Innovationen bewertet. Mit diesen Ergebnissen wurden drei Szenarien mit unterschiedlichen Automatisierungsgraden definiert und die Rangierprozesszeiten für jedes von ihnen unter Berücksichtigung eines Muster-Güterzugs ausgewertet. Diese Analyse zeigt, dass die Implementierung der aktuellen kommerziellen Technologie zu einer Zeitersparnis (ohne Berücksichtigung von Stillstandzeiten) von bis zu 36% gegenüber der derzeitigen Praxis führen würde. Diese Zeitersparnis könnte bis zu 72% betragen, wenn noch nicht marktreife Technologien zur Verfügung stehen würden.

Anzahl der Wörter: 30324

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List of Abbreviations

AI	artificial intelligence
ATO	automatic train operation
ATP	automatic train protection
CCA	cross cutting activities
dGNSS	differential global navigation satellite system
EC	European Commission
ETA	expected time of arrival
EU	European Union
GHG	greenhouse gas
GLONASS	global navigation satellite system
GNSS	global navigation satellite system
GoA	grade of automation
GPS	global positioning service
HF	high frequency
HY	hump yard
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IM	infrastructure manager
IP	innovation programme
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISA	International Society of Automation
ITSS	Industry Platform for Telematics and Sensor Technology
ITU	intermodal transport unit
IVG	intelligent video gate
LoA	level of automation
MY	marshalling yard
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
n.d.	no data
OC	open call
OCR	optical character recognition
RCG	Rail Cargo Group
RFID	radio-frequency identification
RIC	Regolamento Internazionale delle Carrozze
SBB	Schweizerische Bundesbahnen
SNCF	Société Nationale des Chemins de Fer
SOAP	simple object access protocol
SWL	single wagon load
TIS	Technischer Innovationskreis Schienengüterverkehr
TRL	technological readiness level
TSI	technical specifications for interoperability
UHF	ultra-high frequency
UIC	Union Internationale des Chemins de Fer
ZBA	Zugbildungsanlage

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1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the structure and content of this thesis. It also presents information on the motivation for this work and describes the concrete objectives and the research question addressed.

1.1 Background

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), climate change is one of the main short-term threats for humanity. Predictions by the IPCC foresee a vast impact on the planet if greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are not reduced in the coming decades [Field et al. 2014:44]. Aligned with this position, the European Union (EU) wants to gradually reduce GHG emissions, and the European Commission (EC) has defined three future targets to do so. Taken as baseline scenario 1990, the EC expects a 20% cut of GHG emissions by 2020 [The Economist 2014], 40% by 2030 (binding) [Neslen 2014] and 100% by 2050 (vision) [EC 2018:22].

Strategies to reduce the overall GHG emissions by 20% by 2020 have been successful [EUROSTAT 2018b:69]. However, the transport sector did not contribute to this reduction. As shown in Figure 1, GHG emissions in the transport sector have risen by around 20% since 1990.

Figure 1. Percentage change of GHG emissions in CO₂ equivalent for the EU28 since 1990, across several sectors. Source: [EEA 2019]

To break this cycle, the EU has developed a strategy to reduce GHG emissions in the transport sector. A main pillar of this strategy entails boosting the modal

shift from less to more sustainable means of transport. This vision is contained in various documents – among others, in a milestone of this strategy: the publication of the White Paper on Transport. The document defines 10 goals to reduce CO₂ emissions by 60% by 2050, and 40 concrete initiatives to be implemented in the 2010s [EC 2011:1]. One of the 10 goals directly targets a freight modal shift from road to more sustainable modes such as railway or waterborne modes. Two objectives with different time frames were defined: 30% of road freight over 300 km should shift to sustainable transport modes by 2030 and 50% by 2050 [EC 2011:9].

The rail sector is expected to absorb a high percentage of the anticipated freight modal shift. The main European rail freight companies target the ambitious goal of reaching a modal share of 30% by 2030 [Rail Freight Forward 2018]. However, as illustrated in Figure 2, the modal share of the rail freight transport has not changed substantially in Europe, despite the effort during recent years. The shift has ranged between 17% and 19% of the transported tonne-km in Europe. The European Court of Auditors described this evolution as “unsatisfactory” [ECA 2016:8].

Figure 2. Percentage over the total inland freight in tonne-km (EU28). Source: [EUROSTAT 2018a]

Several explanations have been proposed for the slow development. A widely accepted reason is the poor competitiveness of rail versus road. This impacts

especially on the single wagon load (SWL), whose operators face significant barriers to offer a profitable service [Enning et al. 2017b:12]. However, profit is not the only problem. According to Dionori et al. [2015], poor reliability, low flexibility, and high prices are critical issues that make clients reluctant to use rail transport. Meeting these demands is a complex task, since it requires intervention in several rail system components. Among these components, I focus in this thesis on freight yard operations.

Freight yards are a key element of rail freight transport. If the rail network is examined as a set of nodes and edges, freight yards represent the access points to the network and are thus the interface with other means of transport. In addition, these nodes are responsible for many transshipment operations that require clear and efficient shunting procedures. According to Bontekoning et al. [2004:339], up to 50% of the transit time of freight trains is spent in shunting operations. Therefore, the success of freight-yard operation depends on shunting that is as efficient as possible.

For this reason, efficient shunting processes in freight yards are crucial to increase the reliability and efficiency of the whole system. To counter the trend shown in Figure 2, and to improve the competitiveness of the rail-freight sector and revitalize the SWL, one possibility is to use automated shunting.

1.2 Objectives and scope

This work is aimed at deepening the knowledge about shunting automation in freight yards. The objectives of this thesis are two-fold:

1. To provide a comprehensive survey of the current developments in shunting automation in Europe.
2. To explore the potential benefits of the implementation of innovations in freight yards.

The thesis focuses on processes related to train operation. Processes related to other parts of the logistic chain – such as loading or unloading containers – are not analysed. Facilities where operations are centred on the transshipment of units instead of wagon shunting are not analysed in depth. The focus is on the technical processes that occur in freight marshalling yards. This excludes the idle time of wagons in the facilities, since these times are hardly influenced

by the automation of operations in the yard.

In this thesis, “shunting” is understood in a broad sense and not as the mere movement of trains. In this context, shunting includes other auxiliary processes, such as communications and inspection checks.

1.3 Approach

Objective 1 was fulfilled by scientifically mapping articles, technical reports, and strategic documents; and through personal communication and interviews with experts from the industry. These interviews were conducted by phone call (web call) and were focused on automation experiences. Due to data protection issues, the interviews cannot be reproduced in this document and the names of the experts who cooperated are concealed.

The status of current developments was determined by assessing the technological readiness level (TRL).

To assess the potential benefits of increasing the automation level of freight yards, as defined in Objective 2, the time savings derived from implementing the innovations was assessed. The definition of a model train enabled evaluating the process times of the shunting operations in a hump yard for varying levels of automation.

1.4 Structure

Chapter 2 of the thesis describes the different types of rail-freight yards. The chapter includes a classification of freight yards and a description of the main components and their functions.

Chapter 3 discusses the concept of automation. It presents several definitions of the term and describes different approaches across various disciplines. Taxonomies published regarding the rail sector are examined, and a suitable classification of the level of automation (used later in the thesis) is proposed.

A description of the shunting operations performed in a hump yard is provided in Chapter 4. The processes are grouped according to the component of the hump yard where they occur; thereafter, a comprehensive chronological description of the actions and operations is provided. The current process times are assessed based on the definition of a model freight train.

Chapter 5 analyses the state-of-the-art of automated shunting in freight within Europe. The main innovation fields are clustered, and the mapping of strategic documents for the sector in Europe and Germany facilitates the identification of current developments in the field. Initiatives and experiences related to automated shunting are analysed, and the maturity of the innovations is assessed by estimating their TRL. The classification elaborated in Chapter 3 is used to evaluate the level of automation of the innovation fields identified in this chapter.

The findings from the previous chapters provide a basis for the application case developed in Chapter 6. The application case is elaborated by defining three scenarios that represent different levels of automation. Each scenario includes a set of the innovations identified and evaluated in Chapter 5. An assessment of the time processes for each scenario is performed and the results are used to evaluate the time savings that the implementation of innovations in a hump yard would yield. To conclude, the labour-cost savings derived from the time saving are evaluated.

Chapter 7 presents the main findings of the thesis. It also offers suggestions for further developments.

2 Freight rail yards

This chapter provides an introduction to freight rail yards and their various typologies. After a brief explication of the different types of rail freight yards, the chapter focuses on the facilities in which shunting operations play a central role. It finishes with a comparison of the main features of the freight rail yards that were analysed.

Freight rail yards can be defined as facilities in which a train's composition is modified in some way. Wagons or loads are removed, transhipped or added, or the order of the wagons is changed. Yards where trains exclusively stop for buffering without additional operations, such as sidings, are not considered in this work.

Freight rail yards can be divided into several categories. The most common classifications are based on topography [Marinov *et al.* 2009:1107f], the transport modes involved [Marinov *et al.* 2014:180ff] or so-called generations [Boysen *et al.* 2013:2314]. The last classification considers both the transport modes and the object handled (wagon or load). The classification system proposed below incorporates elements of each of these three main classifications.

Figure 3. Freight rail yard classification. Source: Own elaboration

As shown in Figure 3, the first step in the classification is the division according

to the object to be handled: load or wagon. Load transshipment is required (with a few exceptions such as ro-ro transport) if goods will continue travelling in other modes of transport, such as sea or road. In such cases, goods are usually transported in intermodal transport units (ITUs) such as containers, semitrailers or liftable swap bodies.

Load transshipment is also performed in so-called third generation rail-rail terminals [Boysen et al. 2013:314]. An example of this type of facility is the rail component of the intermodal terminal *MegaHub Lehrte* currently in construction in the proximity of Hannover [DB Netze 2017].

Figure 4. Layout of a rail-rail transshipment yard. Source: [Boysen et al. 2013:322]

As illustrated in Figure 4, transshipment of loads among trains is performed by gantry cranes. To enable direct transshipment among inbound and outbound trains, the trains must occupy parallel tracks. This type of facility is frequently equipped with buffer areas to store ITUs and to allow transshipment of loads, without requiring the simultaneous presence of inbound and outbound trains. Since this terminal type is designed to minimize shunting operations, I have not analysed this category in depth.

In marshalling yards (MYs), workers attend to forming and rearranging the trains by shunting. Within MYs, Figure 3 shows the three main categories of this type of facility. According to topography, rail-rail marshalling yards can be divided into three main groups: flat-shunted yards, hump yards and gravity yards [Marinov et al. 2009:1107f]. The next section describes the main

elements and functions of each of the marshalling-yard types.

2.1 Flat-shunted yards

A flat-shunted yard can be defined as a marshalling yard that has a limited slope, in which shunting operations are performed with the help of a shunting locomotive.

Flat-shunted yards have typically been the most widespread rail-freight yard type [Petracek et al. 1977:26]. The reason is that such yards are designed in different sizes and therefore this type offers high flexibility and can perform different functions. Accordingly, the degree of complexity of the rail operations performed in a flat-shunted rail varies greatly.

Flat-shunted facilities can be divided into two main categories according to their function in the rail system. The first category includes facilities that are at (or very close to) the gateway to the rail network. Classic examples are yards belonging to the shipper, where goods are prepared to be transported by rail, or facilities located inside or very close to ports. The second category consists of yards having the main function of performing shunting operations within the rail network. Figure 5 shows the different types of flat-shunted yards.

Yard type number	One-sided or two-sided	No. of switching leads	Separate or non-separate R&D tracks	Schematic Geometry
1	One-sided	One/each end	No separate R&D tracks	
2	One-sided	One/each end	Separate R&D tracks	
3	Two-sided	one/each end/side	No separate R&D tracks	
4	Two-sided	One/each end/side	Separate R&D tracks	
5	One-sided	Multiple leads	No separate R&D tracks	
6	One-sided	Multiple leads	Separate tracks	
7	Two-sided	Multiple leads	No separate R&D tracks	
8	Two-sided	Multiple leads	Separate R&D tracks	

Figure 5. Flat-shunted yards typologies. Source: [Wong P.J. et al. 1981:79]

Figure 5 shows three additional criteria for classifying flat-shunted yards. The

first criterion focuses on the location of the yard: it is “one-sided” if the yard is located only at one side of the track, and “two-sided” if located at both sides. The second criterion is the number of switching leads, consisting of the number of tracks used by the shunting locomotive to move wagons in and out of the classification tracks. The number can vary from one for each end to several tracks.

The last criterion is related to the division of functions in the yard – that is, the arrival and departure of trains. Small flat-shunted yards often do not have parts dedicated to special shunting functions, but this characteristic can facilitate the shunting operations in facilities with high wagon volumes. Another common element of some flat-shunted yards is shunting necks, which are shown in Figure 6 along with the dedicated receiving and departure tracks. Shunting necks facilitate the push-pull operations of the shunting locomotive [Marinov et al. 2009:1107].

Figure 6. Shunting necks in flat-shunted yards. (track prolongations between the words *mainline* and *switch leads*). Source: [Wong P.J. et al. 1981:80]

Flat-shunted yards can handle numerous wagons, but they are labour-intensive because of the many locomotive movements required. Some sources consider the value of 1000 handled wagons per day as a maximum value for this type [Wong P.J. et al. 1981:75]. This reference value must be viewed with caution due to the age of the source and because labour costs may differ widely between different countries. The construction of a flat-shunted yard may also be considered if the available space is limited or if economic resources for constructing the facility are limited [Chandra et al. 2008:469].

2.2 Hump yards

Hump yards (HYs) are defined as marshalling yards where the hump is the central element of the facility for shunting operations. Traditionally, this type has played a key role for SWL traffic – and continues to do so [PwC et al.

2015:51].

Unlike flat-shunted yards, this type is almost always large (see Figure 7). Because of the high construction costs resulting from the size, as well as high operating costs, there are far fewer existing HYs than flat-shunted yards [PwC et al. 2015:56ff]

Figure 7. Generic marshalling yard. Source: Translated from [Hiller 1983:20]

Figure 7 shows the typical schematic HY design in Europe, with serial configuration of its main four components: arrival yard, hump, classification yard, and departure yard. This configuration differs depending on the aim for which the facility was designed. For instance, some HYs have a compact form, without a departure yard – and with the classification yard performing the tasks of a departure yard. In other cases, such as the case shown in Figure 7, additional components (such as a secondary hump) can be added. In countries where the typical length of freight trains is considerably greater than in Europe (e.g. in the USA), some HYs select a parallel configuration of certain components to avoid the facility needing to stretch over a vast area [Pachl 2012:21].

In the following, the main functions of each component of an HY are briefly explained, as derived from Berndt [2001:103f]. The main function of the arrival yard is the management of inbound trains. In the arrival yard, trains are prepared to be shunted over the hump; it also serves as a buffer in case of a high influx of outbound trains. Uncoupled single wagons or cuts are later

pushed by a shunting locomotive over the hump to form new trains. These wagons are guided towards a pre-determined track of the classification yard by a set of switches. In this manner, wagons with the same final or intermediate destination gradually form outbound trains.

The hump process can be repeated by pulling back the wagon to the receiving track for humping again, or by shunting it over a secondary hump to improve the order of the wagons. Once the outbound train is complete, it can be pulled to the departure yard, where it is prepared and waits for permission to leave the HY and enter the network. The processes performed in an HY are described in greater detail in Chapter 4.

A key point in the design of the HY is the dominant direction of the outbound trains. For example, in Figure 7, inbound trains ideally enter the facility by the west side and outbound trains leave by the east side. Although trains coming from the east can also enter the facility and outbound trains can head west, too many inbound and outbound trains running in the direction opposite the dominant pattern can negatively impact the operational efficiency of the HY. In case of high traffic in both directions, two parallel systems can be built, each one with its own hump but with an opposite distribution of their components. This arrangement is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Schematic representation of a double yard. Source: [Pachl 2013:235]

Hump yards are expensive to operate and build; to be profitable, they must be capable of handling many wagons. Some sources consider a minimum value of 1500 handled wagons per day to be profitable [Wong P.J. et al. 1981:75]. This reference value must be viewed with caution because of the age of the source. As a comparison, the largest and second-largest hump yards¹ in Europe,

¹ Measured in kilometres of tracks

namely Maschen and Mannheim, can handle 8000 [Schmidt 2018] and 5600 [Rees 2017:23] wagons per day, respectively.

Furthermore, HYs have lost relevance in Western Europe in recent decades because of the reduction or cancellation of SWL services in several European countries [PwC et al. 2015:32]. This trend extends to North America, where Class I railroad CSX has announced its plans to retrofit some of its HYs into flat-shunted yards [Ziobro 2017]. However, there are also positive trends, such as the recent modernization of the Halle HY in Germany [DB Cargo 2018].

2.3 Gravity yards

Gravity yards are marshalling yards in which shunting operations are performed largely through the slope of the facility. Similar to HYs, gravity yards have played a key role for SWL traffic. This type was used mainly in Germany at the beginning of the 20th century. Outside Germany, pure gravity yards are rather uncommon [Hiller 1983:19].

Figure 9. Generic gravity yard. Source: Translated from Hiller [1983:21]

As shown in Figure 9, the parts and functions of this typology are similar to those of HYs; the figure also illustrates the main difference from the HY. Apart from the entrance of the arrival yard and most of the departure yard, the facility presents a downward slope along the MY, which facilitates the

movement of wagons heading west. Importantly, the slope is steeper around both humps to accelerate the wagon shunting.

An interesting feature of this typology is that it can be combined with a hump. An example is the MY of Hallsberg in Sweden, shown in below.

Figure 10. Marshalling yard (gravity and hump) of Hallsberg, Sweden. Source: [Marinov 2018:17]

Unlike the pure gravity yard in Figure 9, which has no hump, in Hallsberg a hump was added. This means that wagons must be pushed over the hump by a shunting locomotive.

The main advantage of pure gravity yards is the downward slope, which dramatically reduces the use of shunting locomotives. However, this is also their main disadvantage. These facilities require additional technical effort to maintain wagons stopped during idle times [Berndt 2001:105]. Another negative factor compared to HY is lower efficiency, which results from the slow speed at which wagons roll down in the sorting zone [Pachl 2012:22].

The productivity of gravity yards can be as high as hump yards. However, the demanded extra investment, together with higher complexity in the operation, led constructors to avoid this type of MY when building new MY after the mid-20th century [Hiller 1983:118f].

2.4 Chapter summary

To complete this chapter, a comparative table is presented to summarize the

main characteristics of the three rail freight yards types that have been described.

	Flat-shunted	Hump	Gravity
Construction cost	Low-Medium	High	High
Operation cost	Low-Medium	High	Very High
Size	Low-Medium	Large	Large
Complexity	Low-Medium	High	Very High
Number of facilities	High	Low	Very Low
Wagon handling capacity	Low	High	High
Shunting locomotive use	High	Low	Very Low

Table 1. Rail freight yards: comparative table. Source: Own elaboration

As shown in Table 1, gravity yards and HYs show similar overall characteristics. The main differences are their operation costs, the complexity of the MY, and the use of the shunting locomotive. Whereas operation costs and complexity are lower for HYs, the use of shunting locomotives is reduced in gravity yards. Savings derived from the use of relatively little shunting do not compensate for the costs incurred by a more complex operation, which has high labour costs. Evidence of this principle is that the construction of new gravity yards has been discarded and HYs are preferred.

The comparison between hump and flat-shunted yards offers a more nuanced picture. Since flat-shunted yards do not have an alternative manner to move wagons, the intensive use of shunting locomotives is required. However, flat-shunted yards are usually more economic to operate and construct than are HYs, due to less complexity. This leads to the feature of HYs that is both their main handicap and the main advantage: the need to handle large volumes of wagons.

3 What is automation?

This chapter provides an in-depth definition of automation in freight yards. Although a few processes performed in a freight yard could be described as either automated or non-automated, most operations in a freight yard do not fit well with this binary approach. The classification of operations and processes is complicated and requires a gradual analysis. Hence, I discuss different gradual approaches that have been proposed to classify the level of automation (LoA).

The discussion has three phases: the first introduces definitions of automation; the second presents relevant concepts and ideas linked to automation, as well as relevant taxonomies; and the third examines automation taxonomies focused on the rail sector. The chapter concludes with a brief discussion and a suitable definition of LoA criteria to be applied in this work.

3.1 Definitions of automation

The objective of this section is not to provide a detailed review of the concept of automation, but to discuss the background for adopting a suitable definition to be used in later chapters. To this end, I selected several reviews that discuss the concept of automation, among various disciplines.

Before examining complex classifications, a dictionary can provide an initial definition of a term. The *Merriam-Webster Thesaurus* (online) defines “automation” as follows: “*The process of putting an apparatus, operation, or system under the control of regulation of mechanical or electronic devices*” [Merriam-Webster 2019]. *Oxford Dictionaries* (online) includes additional information, situating the origin of the term in the 1940s in the USA: “*The use or introduction of automatic equipment in a manufacturing or other process or facility*” [Oxford Dictionaries 2019]

A more specialized perspective is provided by the International Society of Automation (ISA), which stated that automation is “*the creation and application of technology to monitor and control the production and delivery of products and services.*” [ISA 2019]

A reference work in the manufacturing field, *Fundamentals of Modern Manufacturing: Materials, Processes, and Systems* [Groover 2013:965]

commented as follows:

“Automation can be defined as the technology by which a process or procedure is performed without human assistance.”

In all these definitions, there is a sense of control of processes by utilizing technology. In addition, each definition suggests differing degrees of intervention by technology. The definition by the ISA includes automation to monitor a process, whereas the definition provided by Groover requires total control of the process by technology. As the next sections indicate, the different types of automation play a key role in the discussion.

3.2 Taxonomies of automation

The classifications of automation processes as discussed in published scientific journals indicate that the fields of human factors and industrial manufacturing are the largest contributors. One of the most important and widely-cited publications addressing automation is Parasuraman et al. [2000], from the human factors field. The authors propose a methodology to evaluate the optimal level of automation of a system. Aspects considered are automation reliability, impact on human performance, and the cost of the decision or action outcomes.

Parasuraman et al. (2000) suggest an approach focused on four types of functions: information acquisition, information analysis, decision and action selection, and action implementation. The first three are connected to information handling and the last to task execution. Regarding the LoA, the authors argue that LoA is not a discrete scale but rather a *continuum*. Nonetheless, they proposed a ten LoA scale to classify functions related to the decision and action selection.

A more recent review of approaches and classifications of LoA, also from the human factors field, was provided by Vagia et al. [2016]. The relevance of this article lies in its compilation of taxonomies of LoA developed since the late 1950s. The authors show how diverse the LoA taxonomies developed to date are, collecting many different approaches and thus implicitly suggesting the complexity of the task. The review is shown in Table 2. It includes 12 classifications with varying LoA grades, ranging from 4 to 12 LoA. The authors

grouped LoA into 19 categories, from the lowest level (manual) to the highest (autonomous). Table 2 shows the categories presented in each classification and the numerical LoA assigned to each. For the sake of clarity, the classifications are represented by a Roman numeral instead of the proposer’s name. Further details about each classification appear in the original source.

		Classifications											
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
Categories	Manual	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
	Data Acquisition				2							2	1
	Telepresence					2							
	Manual Control with Intelligent Assistance							2					
	Remotely Operated									2			
	Computer offers decisions	2	1	2	3		2		2	2		3	2
	Narrows down selection	3							7				3
	Director/Agent Control				4,5,6	3			3				
	Shared Control							3	4				
	Suggest one alternative	4											4
	Executes with human approval	5	2	3			3		6			4	5
	Decision Support								5		3		
	Executes if no human veto	6	3	4	7,8		4			3		5	6
	Executes and informs human	7			9							6	7
	Partner				10			4					
	Informs human if asked	8										7	8
	Inform human, if decides	9							8				9
	Supervisor				11	4		5	9				
	Autonomous System	10	4	5	12	5	5		10		4	8	10

Table 2. Taxonomy of LoA classifications. Source: Own elaboration based on data from Vagia et al. [2016:4]

As evident in Table 2, among the 19 categories shown, only five appear more than five times. Apart from the expected categories *Manual* and *Autonomous System*, the categories *Computer offers decisions*, *Executes with human approval* and *Executes if no human veto* are present in most classifications.

Another interesting review, this time from the manufacturing field, was provided by Winroth et al. [2008]. In the articles centred on human factors, the focus is generally on the role that a computer or similar electronic device plays in a process. By contrast, Winroth et al. addressed the problem from a perspective applied to the manufacturing industry. The article builds on two concepts from previous works by other authors, namely *computerization* and *mechanization*. These two concepts distinguish between two types of automation. Mechanization is oriented toward manual work and is defined as the “*replacement of human muscle power*”. Computerization focuses on intellectual work, and is defined as “*the replacement of cognitive tasks*” [Winroth et al. 2008:7].

LoA	Mechanical and Equipment	Information and Control
1	Totally manual - Totally manual work, no tools are used, only the users own muscle power. E.g. The users own muscle power	Totally manual - The user creates his/her own understanding for the situation, and develops his/her course of action based on his/her earlier experience and knowledge. E.g. The users earlier experience and knowledge
2	Static hand tool - Manual work with support of static tool. E.g. Screwdriver	Decision giving - The user gets information on what to do, or proposal on how the task can be achieved. E.g. Work order
3	Flexible hand tool - Manual work with support of flexible tool. E.g. Adjustable spanner	Teaching - The user gets instruction on how the task can be achieved. E.g. Checklists, manuals
4	Automated hand tool - Manual work with support of automated tool. E.g. Hydraulic bolt driver	Questioning - The technology question the execution, if the execution deviate from what the technology consider being suitable. E.g. Verification before action
5	Static machine/workstation - Automatic work by machine that is designed for a specific task. E.g. Lathe	Supervision - The technology calls for the users' attention, and direct it to the present task. E.g. Alarms
6	Flexible machine/workstation - Automatic work by machine that can be reconfigured for different tasks. E.g. CNC-machine	Intervene - The technology takes over and corrects the action, if the executions deviate from what the technology consider being suitable. E.g. Thermostat
7	Totally automatic - Totally automatic work, the machine solve all deviations or problems that occur by it self. E.g. Autonomous systems	Totally automatic - All information and control is handled by the technology. The user is never involved. E.g. Autonomous systems

Table 3. Two-fold scale for mechanization and computerization. Source: [Winroth et al. 2008:19]

Table 3 shows the division between computerized and mechanized tasks, and the descriptions of the seven LoA proposed by the authors for both concepts. Both scales start and finish with manual and autonomous work as the lowest and highest levels of LoA respectively. Apart from the clear separation between the focus on work execution in the mechanized task classification and information handling for computerized tasks, the definition of the highest LoA for mechanization processes is of particular interest. The authors specify that an autonomous device must be capable not only of performing a task without human intervention but also of solving – by itself – any deviations and problems that may arise.

3.3 Taxonomies of automation in the rail sector

LoA classifications related to the transport sector have been present for decades. The air sector pioneered the first classifications of transport-related LoA [Vagia et al. 2016:7]. More recently, the development of highly automated automobiles has prompted new definitions and classifications for the automobile sector [SAE J3016 JUN2018].

Automation in the rail sector is not a new process. It began at the start of modern rail transport, with the development of technologies such as the indirect brake, track circuit, and – in marshalling yards – hump operations. These technologies indicate that automation has been a recurrent topic in rail

research. However, until recently, no specific taxonomies had been developed to describe the degree of automation of any component of the rail sector.

The first step in this direction occurred in the field of train operation. The first taxonomy was presented in 2006 in an initial published version of an international standard of the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) [IEC 62290-1:2014]. Train operation was divided into five grades of automation (GoA). Additional impetus for this development has been the growing number of kilometres of automated metro lines that have been deployed around the world in recent decades [UITP 2016:5].

Basic functions of train operation		On-sight train operation	Non-automated train operation	Semi automated train operation	Driverless train operation	Unattended train operation
		GOA0	GOA1	GOA2	GOA3	GOA4
Ensuring safe movement of trains	Ensure safe route	x (points command/control in system)	system	system	system	system
	Ensure safe separation of trains	x	system	system	system	system
	Ensure safe speed	x	x (partly supervised by system)	system	system	system
Driving	Control acceleration and braking	x	x	system	system	system
Supervising guideway	Prevent collision with obstacles	x	x	x	system	system
	Prevent collision with persons on tracks	x	x	x	system	system
Supervising passenger transfer	Control passengers doors	x	x	x	x	system
	Prevent person injuries between cars or between platform and train	x	x	x	x	system
	Ensure safe starting conditions	x	x	x	x	system
Operating a train	Set in/set off operation	x	x	x	x	system
	Supervise the status of the train	x	x	x	x	system
Ensuring detection and management of emergency situations	Perform train diagnostic, detect fire/smoke and detect derailment, handle emergency situations (call/evacuation, supervision)	x	x	x	x	system and/or staff in OCC
NOTE x = responsibility of operations staff (may be realised by UGTMS system) System = shall be realised by UGTMS system						

Figure 11. GoA for train operation. Source: [IEC 62290-1:2014:14]

Figure 11 shows the relationship between the GoA and the human role in several functions related to train operation. The lowest level (GoA0) describes on-sight train operation without any automatic train operation. The train driver is responsible for train control and route restrictions, such as maximum speed. These restrictions are performed with the support of permanent operating rules (e.g. tokens) or wayside signals.

The next level (GoA1) also refers to non-automated train operation, where the train driver is again fully responsible for the train control. However, GoA1 may include train protection against some risks, such as the overrun of stop signals. For this reason, UITP labels GoA1 as “Automatic Train Protection (ATP) with driver” [UITP 2012:1].

The GoA2 level marks a step further in automation, denoted as “semi-

automated train operation”. This level includes full ATP and some features of automatic train operation (ATO), such as controlled acceleration and braking. However, the train driver must still supervise track conditions and passenger transfer operations, such as opening and closing train doors.

GoA3 is defined as “driverless train operation” and is substantially different from the previous GoA. The presence of the train driver in the control cab is no longer required, because of the implementation of higher levels of ATO and ATP [Keevill 2016:8]. Although track conditions are supervised by the system, human action is still required to operate doors and set the vehicle in motion.

Finally, GoA4 is defined as “*Unattended train operation*”. This is a fully automated system in which nobody is required on-board. If required, the vehicle may be remotely managed by a person.

Another approach within the rail sector is derived from signal engineering. In the framework of a study about the perceived workload for various different LoA, Balfe et al. [2015] proposed a rail automation model based on the four functions identified by Parasuraman et al. [2000]. This classification system distinguishes five levels for each type of function, from fully automatized to fully manual, by adding three additional degrees of cooperation between human and machine.

The difference between autonomous and automated driving established by DB Systel [DB Systel 2017] is interesting. The distinction arises from the place where decisions are made and controlled. In autonomous driving, the control of the vehicle is performed by means of sensors installed in the vehicle and the information is processed without human intervention. Automated driving, by contrast, is defined as the external control of the vehicle.

3.4 Definition of Levels of Automation in this work

As mentioned, the mapping of innovations in freight rail shunting is followed by a classification of several elements according to the degree of automation. To this end, a classification system that could be used for different processes is required. However, as shown later, the processes performed in marshalling yards include a wide range of situations with differing characteristics.

The classification selected for this work was adopted having in mind the scope

of this work. Hence, if the approach to automation as a continuum is accepted (as previously explained), a trade-off is required between operationality and completeness for the proposed classification. A good example is the separation of information processing versus action implementation suggested by Parasuraman et al. [2000]. Although this idea may be interesting for the processes that occur in an MY, this approach implies a detailed description that separates information processes from implementation processes.

To maintain the complexity within reasonable margins while also providing useful information about the level of automation, I propose a scale based on Winroth et al. [2008], with several elements added. Table 4 describes the proposed scale. The classification focuses on the role played in the process by the actor responsible for its execution. The added elements are the distinction between mechanical and digital, and the supervisory role, derived from Table 2. These elements should provide enough flexibility to facilitate a description of the LoA considering the variety of tasks performed in an MY.

LoA	Description
LoA0	The task is performed manually by a human
LoA1	The task is performed by a mechanical device activated by a human
LoA2	The task is performed by a digital device activated by a human
LoA3	The task is performed autonomously by the system and supervised by a human
LoA4	The task is performed by the system without human supervision

Table 4. Definition of LoA. Source: Own elaboration

In addition to the classification, I present the process of increasing the automation by integrating several tasks in a largest task, without necessarily increasing the LoA (as defined in Table 4). This idea is presented in Figure 12, which shows different paths to increase the automation of a process. These ideas are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 12. Paths for increase in automation. Source: Own elaboration

The initial process (0) can increase the LoA from LoA2 to LoA3 (1). Another possibility is that the initial process is integrated with other processes. Thus, the LoA of both processes remains the same but integration is higher (2). The third path is a combination; it blends integration with other processes plus an increase in the LoA from LoA2 to LoA3 (3).

The increase of automation through integration is a common approach in MY automation. An example can be found in hump automation, where several subprocesses that were previously performed separately have been progressively grouped into one large overall process.

4 Description of the shunting process

The following description of the shunting process is based on a generic hump marshalling yard (HY). This is justified by the fact that rail-related processes performed in gravity and flat-shunted freight yards are also performed to some extent in HYs. Given the lack of hump-related processes in flat-shunted and (pure) gravity yards, the opposite is not true. The idea of transmitting the details of processes at the operational level from an HY to other yard types also appears in the literature (e.g. Boysen et al. [2012:3]).

Figure 13. Components of a marshalling yard. Source: [Marinov 2018:26]

The generic HY used as a reference is illustrated in Figure 13. This sketch shows the basic components of the facility as well as the links between them and the surrounding network. As mentioned in Chapter 2, essential elements of the HY are the arrival and classification yards. Both are connected in Figure 13 with two solid lines, representing two possible itineraries: via track with hump and via flat track. The other solid lines represent the connection of the HY to the surrounding network. Dotted lines represent connections among other common components of the HY, which are not always present. They include a storage yard, a second hump and a departure yard. The dotted lines also show possible connections to the surrounding network. Auxiliary elements of the facility (e.g. storage tracks for locomotives and damaged wagons, and washing and fuelling tracks) are not shown in Figure 13.

4.1 Shunting processes

Different events, steps and procedures are described in this section in chronological order, and according to the place of the wagon within and outside the HY. For the process description, I focus on a wagon that enters the HY as part of an incoming train and leaves the HY as a part of a different outbound train.

Processes within an HY differ in degree from operator to operator, and from country to country, but they share a similar logic. For the description of the shunting process in an HY, I used as a reference a generic large German HY with three components: arrival, classification and departure yard. Most of the information was derived from German sources and was complemented with data from other European countries.

4.1.1 Pre-arrival and entry

Processes to handle inbound wagons start before the train enters the facility. The HYs possess information about arriving trains, but this information has different degrees of accuracy [*Boysen et al. 2012:3*]. Typical information includes the expected time of arrival (ETA) of the scheduled trains [*Marinov 2018:36*]. However, such data may be incomplete or inaccurate, or must be modified. Hence, an information exchange between the infrastructure manager (IM) and the yard operator occurs before the inbound train enters the HY. Data such as ETA, train composition, type of goods, and train length are transmitted to the yard operator. This information exchange occurs in several ways and with different degrees of anticipation [*Marinov 2018:31*].

Finally, before the home signal shows “proceed” and enables the train to enter the facility, the HY must assign a track in the arrival yard. A secured route must also be provided to the assigned track.

The information exchange and the degree of precision of such data are a major issue in the efficient operation of HYs [*DB Cargo 2017:3*]. Marked ETA deviations are commonplace [*Trafikverket 2018:49*] and negatively impact the HY’s operations [*Boysen et al. 2012:3*].

4.1.2 Arrival yard

The description of processes performed in this yard includes processes from the arrival of wagon at the HY until the wagon is pushed over the hump by the hump locomotive. This description is based on Homeyer et al. [*2000:51; 180–190*], complemented with information from other sources.

Once the inbound train reaches its final position in the track assigned by the MY, the mainline locomotive is moved away. First, the brake pipe is emptied [*Pachl 2013:236*] and HY staff uncouple the locomotive and disconnect the

brake pipe. The mainline locomotive then receives a route from the HY operator to the locomotive storage track or to the next operation required, such as pulling the next outbound train [*Marinov 2018:29*].

If wagons stand for more than 60 min or if the slope is more than 2.5‰, the wagons must be secured (e.g. by activating the handbrake) to prevent unintentional movement [*DB RiL 915:0107V03*]. Afterwards, specialized staff perform a technical inspection of the train immediately. This inspection includes checking the train's composition by comparing the inbound train with the information received and seeking possible wagon defects.

A list of the wagons' characteristics (e.g. priority, destination, load, and wagon order) is compiled and compared with the documentation provided by the train driver or by electronic means. The list is transmitted and used for the subsequent hump operations. The end-of-train device, which ensures the train's completeness, must be removed from the last wagon. Staff must indicate which wagons cannot be humped and will be flat-shunted. Reasons for this may include being damaged or loaded with dangerous goods.

Once the technical inspection is finished, and assuming that the inbound train does not have to wait to be handled, technical preparations for wagon humping begin. The staff receives a list with the *cuts*, referring to a single wagon or a set of wagons that will be humped as a unit. The list specifies which couplers must be prepared for humping. The preparation starts with closing the brake valves of the involved cuts and disconnecting the brake pipe. Then the couplers are either loosened if there is a descending slope before the hump, or completely released if there is no descending slope. This aspect depends on the HY design [*Pachl 2012:23*].

All these operations are performed by specialized staff, even in the most modern HYs [*Enning et al. 2017b:13*]. Wagons that cannot be humped are flat-shunted to the required destination, such as a storage track (for damaged wagons) or the departure yard (for dangerous goods).

Table 5 below shows the timeframes for common processes performed in the arrival yard, for a generic freight train. The train used as a reference here was based on König et al. [*2018a:659f*] and was a 524-m long train (locomotive included) with 23 wagons distributed in 16 cuts.

PROCESS	START	END	MINUTES
Uncoupling and moving mainline locomotive away	0	4	4
Technical inspection and documentation	0	23	23
Train preparation for humping	23	53	30
TOTAL			53

Table 5. Process times in the arrival yard. Source: Own elaboration based on König et al. [2018a:660], Simonovic [2019:24], and DB Cargo [2017:36].

The times shown in Table 5 represent the handling of inbound trains in a digitalized facility, in which documentation and transmission of information are assisted by electronic devices. It is assumed that there is no need to loosen couplers before humping, and that brake hands are either not activated or the process time required for this is brief.

Time data were obtained from various sources. Locomotive uncoupling and release times were derived from Simonovic [2019:24]. Technical inspection times were based on DB Cargo [2017:36], which allow a minute for each wagon. This time includes the preparation of the humping documentation and the release of the end-of-device train, as well as checking for damages in the inbound train. The times for preparing the train for humping were based on König et al. [2018a:660]. It was assumed that only 15 couplers must be prepared for humping and that each process required 40 sec. In addition, the responsible person walks at 0.8 m/s. Walking in one direction, the person decouples wagons, and on the way back closes the brake valves.

4.1.3 Classification yard

The processes performed in this yard start with pushing the cuts over the hump and finish when the final outbound composition is pulled to the departure yard. Processes described in this section correspond, where possible, to a modernized large German HY. The modernization programme started in 2002 in accordance with the German Federal Transport Plan (*Bundesverkehrswegeplan*) [Klinke et al. 2012:25].

Hump productivity is a main factor in the overall productivity of marshalling yards [Pachl 2013:249]. Hence, operations related to the automation of this process have received early attention. Partial automated operation of the hump and associated wagon-braking operations existed as long ago as in the 1950s in the USA [Chicago, Milwaukee, St. Paul and Pacific Railroad 1952:2]. The

trend towards automating hump processes has continued to date and the implementation in regular operation of systems with growing complexity has increased worldwide [Bahr et al. 2012; Klinke et al. 2012; Weizhong 2017].

Complexity is not limited to the operation itself but extends to planning. Within all processes related to operational planning in marshalling yards, wagon sorting is the most important [Boysen et al. 2012:4]. Therefore, before describing the sequence of operations performed in the classification yard, I briefly review the operative planning issues here. This overview is complemented with a description of the required infrastructure for the automation of the classification-yard processes.

Two shunting activities dominate wagon sorting in the classification yard. The first is called *roll-in* and consists of pushing wagons downhill over the hump. All incoming wagons must go through this process (except in cases mentioned in the previous section). The second activity is called *pull-back* and consists of pulling back a wagon to the arrival yard to be resorted. This process is not as common as *roll-in*; it depends on the sorting approach used in the freight yard [Gestrelus et al. 2017:3].

The predominant operation type is determined by the configuration of the HY, namely whether it was designed with a secondary sorting yard. The operational type is also determined by the desired output of the sorting process: either sorted according to destination alone, or according to destination plus order composition [Boysen et al. 2012:4]. The exclusive use of roll-in versus roll-in together with pull-back accounts for the different sorting processes shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Sorting process classification in hump yards. Source: own elaboration based on [Boysen et al. 2012:4ff]

As illustrated in Figure 14, sorting approaches are divided into two groups, single-stage and multi-stage. Single-stage means wagons cannot be *pulled back* (strict single-stage) or can be pulled back once in exceptional circumstances (extended single-stage). In multi-stage, wagons can be *pulled back* several times [Boysen et al. 2012:4ff]. These operations are performed, in automated HY, with the help of the infrastructure shown below.

Figure 15. Components of a classification yard. Source: [Weizhong 2017:13]

Figure 15 shows common components for hump automation in modern HYs, grouped into three main categories: speed regulation, switch machines and measuring equipment. Although not shown in Figure 15, close-up devices are usually part of the equipment [Homeyer et al. 2000:222].

The process starts with a hump locomotive pushing wagons over the hump. A hump locomotive is driven behind the train composition and pushes it at a speed of up to 3 m/s [Pachl 2012:24]. In modern HYs in Germany, the hump locomotive is driven by a driver to the cut to be humped, but the pushing of wagons is remotely controlled by the hump operator [Cichon et al. n.d.:1]. If the couplers were only loosened, an operator must release them completely using a long bar [VBG 2013:28]. In addition, the list of wagons and their properties is loaded in the computer that controls and monitors the process.

The description in this paragraph corresponds to Klinke et al. [2012:29f]. Once the wagon reaches the hump crest, it starts rolling downhill by gravity. The wagon data (e.g. axle load, length) are measured by sensors (e.g. radar, sensor weight) and the data are compared and corrected, if necessary. A set of remote-controlled switches and brake systems controls and monitors the direction and

speed of each wagon until it reaches to the previously determined track of the classification yard.

Once the wagon reaches the assigned track, if it did not stop close enough, a close-up system automatically pulls the wagon towards the last wagon standing on the track. The last step before the composition can be pulled to the departure yard entails coupling the wagons and connecting the brake pipes; this must always be done manually. To this end, a shunting locomotive pushes all the wagons to compress the composition, which enables the coupling of wagons and the connection of the brake pipe [Pachl 2013:236].

If wagons must be sorted again, they are pulled back again by flat-shunting to the arrival yard. If the HY has a secondary sorting yard, the cut may instead be pushed over the hump again.

It is evident that processes linked to the classification yard are already highly automated. According to Klinke et al. [2012:31], for facilities with a performance of up to 200 wagons per hour (w/h), the whole process must be controlled by the following personnel: two hump operators, a person responsible for data handling between different data systems and data monitoring, a hump locomotive driver, and staff for coupling and decoupling of wagons.

Table 6 shows an illustrative timeframe for the processes performed in the classification yard and the hump for the train. The values were used as a reference.

PROCESS	START	END	MINUTES
Moving hump locomotive to the composition	0	5	5
Pushing wagons towards the hump	5	7	2
Pushing wagons over the hump + last wagon	7	12	5
Moving shunting locomotive to the composition	12	17	5
Coupling wagons and connecting brake pipe	17	47	30
Pulling composition to the departure yard	47	51	4
TOTAL			51

Table 6. Process times in the classification yard. Source: Own elaboration based on Simonovic [2019:25], König et al. [2018a:661] and DB Cargo [2017:36]

The times displayed in Table 6 represent times for handling inbound trains in a digitalized facility at an arrival yard. The preparation of documentation and transmission of information are mainly made with the help of electronic

devices. The sorting process is a strict single-stage without pull-back.

Time data were obtained from different sources. Locomotive movement times were derived from *Simonovic [2019:25]*. The time required to push wagons towards the hump was calculated at a speed of 2.2 m/s [*König et al. 2018a:661*] and a distance to the crest of the hump of 270 m [*DB Cargo 2017:36*]. The same value, 2.2 m/s, was selected for pushing wagons over the hump. An additional minute was added to include the time needed for the last wagon to roll down the hump. The times for wagon coupling and brake connections were assumed to be similar to those required in the arrival yard. The time for pulling the composition was calculated assuming an average speed of 10 km/h and a distance of 700 m (500 m of wagons plus 200 m).

4.1.4 Departure yard

The description of processes performed in this yard includes those performed from the arrival of a wagon at the departure yard until it leaves the HY. The description is mainly based on *Homeyer et al. [2000:43f]*. Additional sources are indicated in the text.

The shunting locomotive first pulls the set of wagons from the classification yard and the shunting locomotive is uncoupled. Then, the set of wagons is prepared and transformed into an outbound train ready to run. Flat-shunted wagons, if any exist, are pulled to the track where the wagons are waiting before preparation starts.

The preparation process starts with the manual coupling of the mainline locomotive as well as the wagons, and the manual connection of the brake pipe. Brake calculation of the train and a full brake test are performed, and the wagon order is checked and the wagons are inspected. Before the signalling gives the approval to leave the HY, the end-of-train device must be installed.

Some of these processes are similar to those performed in the arrival yard. Among the new processes, two are especially relevant because they are time consuming, namely the train and wagon inspection and the full brake test [*NEE 2019:20f*]. In the following paragraphs, these processes are explained in detail. As discussed later in this thesis, the two processes are related.

According to *Marks-Fährmann et al. [2018:429]*, in Germany, the processes of

train inspection and a technical wagon inspection are performed before the outbound train leaves the HY. Train inspection is a visual inspection of the train that focuses on safety in the train's operation. Train inspection includes checking the wagon order. It is recommended to perform this process along with the full brake test.

Technical wagon inspection focuses on the technical state of the wagons. This inspection searches for defects in several parts of the train, such as the wheels and suspension system. It is again recommended to carry out the technical inspection together with the full brake test. Regarding the brake test, according to the German regulations for the HY, a full brake test must be performed in the following cases [*Marks-Fährmann et al. 2018:240*]:

- 1) At the earliest, 24h before train departure (for new train compositions)
- 2) If train has been parked for more than 24 hours

The test involves preparations before the test itself is performed. The test is performed in several phases by authorized staff, who may comprise either two employees (train driver and shunting employee) or one employee (if the locomotive is radio controlled).

The brake test requires compressed air to fill the main brake pipe. Hence, the test is performed by a locomotive (Tfz in Figure 16) or a stationary trackside air crane; these two options lead to slightly different test procedures. The procedures described below relate to a brake test performed with a locomotive. The description of the brake test was obtained from [*DB RiL 915*], unless otherwise stated.

Before the brake test itself is performed, a pre-inspection of the train composition occurs. During this operation, the following steps are completed:

- 1) Friction brakes are installed
- 2) Wagons are properly coupled
- 3) Main brake pipe is properly connected and valves opened
- 4) Defined braking regime is set (e.g. G, P)
- 5) Defined wagon load is set (e.g. loaded, empty)

After the pre-inspection (Z in Figure 16), the main brake pipe is filled to 5 bar and the wagon axles are checked to confirm that the brakes are released (L in Figure 16). Both pre-inspection and the brake-release check can be performed

together to save time (Z/L Figure 16).

Figure 16. Description of a full brake test for a freight train. Source: [DB RiL 915:0103A01]

Then, the main brake pipe tightness is checked by measuring in the locomotive the pressure drop in the pipeline for 1 min (Dh). Then the pressure in the main pipe is lowered by up to 4.2 bar and each axle is visually or manually inspected by an employee to check if the brakes are applied (B). If hand brakes may interfere with the brake test, they must be released and applied after the check. Afterwards, the pressure is increased again up to 5 bar (L) and an additional verification is performed. The valve of the main brake pipe in the last wagon of the composition is opened for at least 15 sec to check the air flow through the whole pipe (D-HL). This is verified by inspecting the brake application of the last wagon (B). Finally, the main brake pipe is filled, and the brakes of all wagons are released and checked by an employee (L). After the procedure has been finished, documentation reflecting the test output is prepared.

In addition to the full brake test, there are other circumstances in an MY where a simplified brake test is required. There are two cases where this may happen in an MY [Marks-Fährmann et al. 2018:242]:

- 1) In a shunting operation when wagons are connected to the main brake pipe

- 2) If the full brake test has been performed by a stationary air crane or by a locomotive that will not haul the outbound train

Figure 17 shows the schematic procedure for the simplified brake test for case 2). The main difference between the simplified and full brake tests is that the simplified test focuses on the last wagon of the composition. This avoids the need to walk past the train and saves time.

Figure 17. Example of simplified brake test. Source: [DB RiL 915:0104A01]

As shown in Figure 17 , the simplified test includes only some of the steps of the full brake test. The main brake pipe is filled and the release of the brakes of the last wagon is checked (L). The proper function of the main brake pipe is checked by opening the valve of the last wagon of the composition (D-HL) and checking whether the brakes of the last wagon are applied (B). Finally, the main brake pipe is filled again and the release of the brakes of the last wagon is checked (L). The brakes of all wagons are released and checked by an employee (L). After the procedure is finished, the documentation reflecting the test output is prepared.

The full brake test requires a person to walk the whole distance of the train at least six times, including the pre-inspection. SBB estimates that a full brake test for a 500-m train requires 40 min [Railway Gazette 2018b]. Typical times in Europe vary from 45 to 60 min for freight trains shorter than 700 m [Troche et al. 2018:15].

Table below shows an illustrative timeframe of the common processes performed in the departure yard, for a generic freight train. The times can be

compared to those for the other types of yard. The generic outbound freight train considered has the same characteristics as the inbound train.

TASKS	START	END	MINUTES
Uncoupling and moving shunting locomotive away	0	5	5
Moving and coupling mainline locomotive to the composition	5	10	5
Train and wagon inspection	10	25	15
Full brake test	25	55	30
Train dispatch	55	58	3
TOTAL			58

Table 7. Process times in the departure yard. Own elaboration based on Simonovic [2019:25f], König et al. [2018a:661], DB Cargo [2017:36] and Troche et al. [2018:15]

As in the previous HY components, the times displayed in Table 7 represent times for handling outbound trains in a digitalized facility, where the documentation and information are electronically prepared and transmitted.

Time data come from different sources. Shunting movement times for the locomotives come from [Simonovic 2019:25]. The train and wagon inspection times were estimated by considering the time for a full brake test, namely 45 min [Troche et al. 2018:15], divided into three 15-min intervals. This allows 15 min for the pre-inspection walk, which includes brake checking, and 30 min for the two required walks for the brake test itself. Finally, some time was added for the train-dispatching process [Simonovic 2019:26] including the installation of the end-of-train device.

4.1.5 Processes and elements beyond yard components

Several elements and processes that are not performed exclusively in a single part of the HY in this work have not yet been analysed. This includes, among others, the planning operation of the facility, the transmission of information, and processes not limited to a specific HY component. Unless otherwise stated, the material used in this section was obtained from [DB Cargo 2017] and was based on the HY of Mannheim.

Several stakeholders are involved in the MY operations. Although their number varies across countries in Europe, four actors having specific functions are usually identified:

- 1) Infrastructure owner
- 2) Infrastructure manager (related to signalling control and movement

- authorisation)
- 3) Marshalling and shunting operator (responsible for the shunting operations)
- 4) Operator of incoming and outgoing trains (freight railway undertakings)

In Germany, the two first functions are performed by DB Netz and the third by DB Cargo. However, all operators have access on equal terms to the services of the MY as a freight railway undertaking. In other countries, all functions could be performed by the same stakeholder or by four different stakeholders.

For daily operations, a plan with a sequence of activities to be performed in the HY is prepared. The plan includes the type of activity and the planned time, with a high degree of detail. This plan is monitored by the yard staff through comparing planned and actual times. If there are deviations from the plan, which is common in HY Mannheim, the dispatchers use the information available from the various IT systems for ad-hoc operation rescheduling. Decisions are based on the dispatchers' experience and knowledge. The most common cause of deviation lies in the delays of incoming trains. Other problems include the lack of personnel, insufficient braking capacity, and excess weight of outbound trains.

Regarding the information produced by and transmitted to the HY, many diverse tools are used, which contributes to the complexity of the operation. In the HY, nine IT applications are used for different operations, including locomotive disposition, the monitoring of deviations of incoming trains, and support wagon inspection. In the case of the HY, all IT applications apart from the one that informs about incoming trains (DB Netz) belong to the MY operator, DB Cargo. In addition to the IT applications for transmitting information in the HY, according to [Marks-Fährmann et al. 2018:390], operative information is transmitted among staff in various ways. These methods are either oral (spoken aloud, by radio, by speakers, or via a third person), by signalling or in written form.

The HY operates 24 h every day in a three-shift system. The staff of the HY comprises 17 profiles, including (among others) shunting locomotive drivers, signallers, train inspectors, and brake testers. On the MY, the staff follow a

strict process before shunting operations are performed, to guarantee the safety of the participants. The highly regulated process includes, among others, clear communication between participants, checking the correct position of switches, and no danger of collision with objects or people [Marks-Fährmann et al. 2018:383ff]. In addition, the maximum speed for shunting is 25 km/h. The same strict regulations are followed to secure the vehicle, according for example to the number of axles or the slope, once the operation is finished.

An important element is the switching points. Although some points in an MY may be remotely controlled by the signaller, points are usually operated by the staff in small to medium-sized facilities. There are two possibilities: points can be manually switched or electrically operated from a display placed at the MY. Usually a set of points can be operated from the same display, saving time and resources [Marks-Fährmann et al. 2018:408f]. However, there are commercial solutions to centrally control and monitor signalling and interlocking systems of a large MY [Pintsch Tiefenbach 2012:2ff; Siemens 2012:2ff]. These systems are mainly used for automating hump operations. They have been installed in large German HYs in recent years [Klinke et al. 2012:28ff] to reduce the need for manual point switching.

4.2 Chapter summary

This summary reviews the processes to be performed in an HY together with an assessment of the time required for each process. It is important to highlight that the time assessment was performed without including any idle time. Figure 18 presents an overview of the handling times.

Figure 18. Process time assessment for an HY. Source: Own elaboration.

So far in this chapter, processes have been described and grouped according to the physical location where they occur. However, in Figure 18, the processes are grouped according to different planning stages. Processes depicted with the same colour are usually performed in a consecutive manner or at the same time without substantial interruptions. The reason for representing processes in this manner is that during real operations in HYS, the process for handling the wagons is not performed in a consecutive manner.

Once a set of processes depicted in the same colour is performed, there is usually a pause [Gestrelius et al. 2017:2]. The pause marked “1” in Figure 18 represents the pause between operations related to the inbound train. Afterwards, the inbound train may have to wait to be humped as other cuts may be pushed over the hump. The pause marked “2” in Figure 18 represents the time in which wagons wait in the classification yard until the outbound train is full, or wait for the scheduled time of departure. Additional analysis of the data in Figure 18 appears in Section 6.1.1.

5 State of the art in automated shunting

As described in Chapter 4, current shunting practices are a mix of highly automated and manual processes. As in the rest of the rail sector, certain shunting processes have been automated since the beginning of modern railways. Reasons for process automation in the rail sector have been diverse. Increase in operational safety and better worker conditions are elements often cited [Egger et al. 2019:18]. Recently, the lack of personnel, especially in German-speaking countries [Fessler et al. 2019:64], and cost pressure from competing with other modes have been added [PwC et al. 2015:10]. In this chapter, the state of the art of automated shunting in Europe and Germany is reviewed and the status of each innovation is assessed.

5.1 Methodology

To evaluate the progress of shunting automation, a four-pronged approach was adopted: 1) selection and clustering of innovations, 2) researching experiences and projects related to the selected innovations, 3) extraction of key technologies for each innovation and 4) classification according to their technological progress. Figure 19 illustrates the flow of this section of the chapter.

Figure 19. Workflow of Section 5.1. Source: Own elaboration

The first step consisted of mapping relevant documents to select the main fields of research linked to automated shunting in freight yards. In the following, research projects and field experiences regarding the topics defined are mapped. Key technologies in the progress of each innovative field identified in the mapped projects are described and discussed. Finally, the key technologies are assessed according to their level of automation and technological progress. This four-step process provides an overview of the state of automated shunting and offers insights into the main technical difficulties to be overcome.

5.1.1 Selection of innovation fields

As described in Chapter 4, shunting involves numerous processes and sub-processes of different kinds and with varying degrees of complexity. This variety makes the selection and clustering of innovations difficult to systematize. However, some support points were used as a reference for starting the work. These points of support consisted of relevant strategic documents related to innovation in freight rail transport, at the German and European levels.

The documents used for reference included the *S2R Multi-Annual Action Plan* (S2R MAAP) [S2R JU 2015] and the *German Rail Freight Masterplan* [BMVI 2017]. Due to its relevance, the document *Weißbuch Intelligenter Güterzug* [TIS 2019c] by the *Technischer Innovationskreis Schienengüterverkehr* (TIS) was also analysed. The TIS promotes the “5L Strategy”² [TIS 2019b] and comprises key stakeholders of the freight rail transport in Germany and Switzerland – such as relevant operators, suppliers and leasing companies [TIS 2019a]. The documents were reviewed and topics linked to innovation in shunting operations were extracted, as listed in Table 8.

S2R MAAP	Rail Freight Masterplan	TIS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •ATO •GNSS for safe train application •Automatic coupling •Telematics and electrification •Real-time yard management •Intelligent video gate terminal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Automation of train formation in MYs •Automation of manual processes (braking, decoupling, connecting brakes) •Automated shunting locomotives •Automation of wagon inspection (video analytics) •Automated inspection of the order of wagons in freight train •Real-time monitoring of shunting processes •Optimization of shunting processes •Automatic and semi-automated coupling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Automated brake test •Calculation of braking capability •Train integrity •Order of wagons in freight trains •Technical inspections of wagons •Digital automated coupling •Energy supply for freight wagons

Table 8. Innovation topics in the German and European agenda. Source: S2R MAAP [S2R JU 2018a:39ff], German Rail Freight Masterplan [BMVI 2017:22] and Weißbuch Intelligenter Güterzug [TIS 2019c:35]

As expected, some innovation fields overlap between the German and European agendas. Given the diverse nature of the documents, the innovations

² Low-Noise, Lightweight, Long-running, Logistic-enabled, Life Cycle Cost-oriented

listed in Table 8 describe elements at different levels. While S2R includes a mixture of high-level and concrete objectives, the Rail Freight Master Plan – and especially the TIS – focus on more concrete aspects. However, the innovations listed in the table can be clustered in the groups shown in Figure 20. It is important to note that certain innovations and technologies are relevant to more than one innovation cluster; this point is discussed later.

Figure 20. Clustering of innovations cited in German and European strategic documents. Source: Own elaboration

Three large clusters were identified: automated shunting vehicles, automated freight wagons, and automated yard operation. In addition, two topics of special interest, which could have been included in at least one of the three clusters, were analysed separately. These are automated coupling and the automation of brake tests.

5.1.2 Review of research projects and experiences

For each innovation cluster defined in the previous section, completed studies and ongoing experiences and research projects performed in recent years related to automated shunting were explored. The review of national and international initiatives enabled the identification of key technologies for each innovation cluster.

The exploration concentrated on Europe and Germany, but experiences from other geographic areas were included if they were highly relevant. The search for relevant experiences outside of Europe yielded rather modest results. In addition, the experts consulted were not aware of significant innovations in automated shunting beyond Europe [Expert#1; Expert#2; Expert#3]. Expert 2 mentioned a Russian initiative about shunting automation. This initiative, MALS, is included in section 5.2.3.

With the aim of systematizing the work, I used the timeframe of the S2R programme as a reference. The S2R programme was started in 2014 and the first projects began in 2015, with some still in progress at the time of writing. This timeframe was also adopted for the selection of other projects and experiences.

Regarding the selection of European projects and experiences, due to the nature of the S2R initiative (a joint undertaking with public and private funding) [S2R JU n.d.], most of the international rail innovations developed at the European level are performed under this initiative.

Figure 21. S2R Innovation Programmes (IPs) and Cross Cutting Activities (CCA). Source: [S2R JU 2018a:40]

As displayed in Figure 21, the S2R initiative is built on five Innovation Programmes (IPs) and covers various subsystems within the rail sector [S2R JU 2018a:40]. Because it was impossible to review all projects of each IP, I focused on projects developed under the IP dedicated to rail freight. This is

IP5, called *Technologies for sustainable and attractive European freight*. A table of the finished and ongoing IP5 projects with additional information appears in the Appendices.

The selection of relevant German research projects and experiences could not be organized in the same way as the European ones. Freight rail innovation initiatives at a national level are promoted, founded and performed by diverse actors, including universities and research centres, industry, the national rail holding, and public administration. Differing degrees of cooperation exist among them. Given this variety, available information sources about rail research and experiences usually offer fragmented and limited information. Hence, selection was based on a combination of internet research, database consultation, literature review and personal communication. Relevant initiatives in Switzerland and France were also included. Further information about the national initiatives appears in the Appendices.

5.1.3 Classification of the key technologies

Each key technology analysed in the previous chapter was classified according to two parameters: LoA, defined in section 3.4; and the technological maturity of the innovations. This maturity level was assessed using the Technological Readiness Level (TRL) scale, developed originally by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) during the 1970s and 1980s to assess the maturity of new technologies linked to the space industry [EARTO 2014]. The TRL scale used in the current study (see Figure 22) was based on the proposal by the EC for assessing the degree of maturity of new technologies developed under the programme Horizon 2020 [EC 2014:29].

Figure 22. TRL scale description. Source: Own elaboration based on [NASA/AS 2005] and [EC 2014:29]

As evident from Figure 22, the scale is composed of nine levels. The TRL 9 level is the highest level of maturity, where the technology has been tested in regular operation. The TRL 1 level is the lowest, where the technology is at an initial stage of development and only basic principles have been observed.

5.2 Innovation fields

In this section I analyse, discuss and assess technologies that are relevant to the automation of shunting processes, as documented in research projects and field experiences. The chapter follows the structure shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23. Structure of Section 5.2. Source: Own elaboration

The review starts with two innovations considered of special relevance. It ends with the three innovation clusters, where automated coupling and automated brake test are integrated.

5.2.1 Automated coupling

Automated coupling is one of the most important elements, if not the most important, for the further development of automated shunting. This is due to its enabling role for other processes, such as the power supply and data transmission and connectivity along the train. The possibility of remote control of the decoupling of wagons is also important [S2R JU 2015:637]. In addition, it can be expected that improvement in the automation of coupling/decoupling processes will yield savings in time and resources [König et al. 2018b:85-86].

Coupling systems can be grouped in three categories according to the degree of automation. The categories are shown in Figure 24 and comprise manual, semi-automated and automated systems.

Figure 24. Coupling types according to their degree of automation. Source: Own elaboration based on [Stuhr 2013:25]

The current manual-screw coupler used in Western and Central Europe was introduced in 1861 [Salger et al. 2018:444]. This system, turned into the European standard [DIN EN 15566:2016:9], presents known weaknesses in comparison with other popular couplers used in other continents, such as the Russian SA3. Its main issue is the need for direct manual intervention in the coupling and uncoupling of wagons [Carrillo et al. 2015:50].

Although solutions for replacing the screw coupling on a large scale have been proposed, none has been implemented [Egger et al. 2019:19]. DB Cargo, in the framework of the ZBA 4.0 project, is working on a robot for coupling and decoupling wagons that are equipped with screw couplers [Expert#2].

As illustrated in Figure 24, semi-automated couplings facilitate the coupling of wagons. The coupling takes place when a wagon is pushed against other vehicle equipped with a compatible automated or semi-automated coupling. The existing semi-automated systems on the market that are in regular operation, mainly outside Europe, are diverse. In addition to the SA3, the Janney coupling is in widespread use worldwide. Other systems, such as the Z-AK and C-AKv, were developed by German companies but have not been widely implemented [Stuhr 2013:29ff]. It is therefore clear that this technology already exists, and its technical feasibility has been probed.

The range of tested and available automated coupling configurations is smaller. A common automated coupling system is the Scharfenberg coupling [Stuhr 2013:40]. It is used in many passenger trains, and the Type 10 – similar to the Scharfenberg – is the TSI standard for high-speed trains in Europe

[Funke 2017:20].

In addition to time and labour cost savings derived from the automated coupling and decoupling process, the connection of the main brake pipe is a relevant issue. As shown in Figure 24, automated coupling includes automated pipe connection, but that is not the case for semi-automated coupling, for which this feature depends on the model. The couplers mentioned above, Z-AK and C-AKv, include automated brake pipe connection, whereas SA3 does not [Stuhr 2013:40].

Another key element for shunting automation is the options offered regarding the automation of auxiliary connections. Cables for transmitting data (UIC-cable) and electrical energy (e.g. RIC-heating cable) are uncommon in freight transport [Funke 2017:12]. However, this feature has high potential for other automation-related applications. If the auxiliary lines must be connected, it should be manually done for screw couplers and some semi-automated couplers.

Several initiatives have been testing and developing automated and semi-automated coupling systems for freight; several projects and experiences have been documented. In the Swiss context, SBB Cargo has been testing a semi-automated centre coupler for wagons developed by Voith, called the *Voith CargoFlex Type Scharfenberg*, within the framework of the *5L-Zug* project [Voith n.d.]. The new device is based on a Type 10 coupler [Railway Gazette 2019]. It is designed to incorporate additional features in the future, such as data transmission and power-supply lines [Voith 2018:2] and an automated uncoupling mechanism [Voith n.d.]. The modernized rolling stock entered into regular operation in May 2019 [SBB Cargo 2019]. Standards to integrate auxiliary connections into the automated coupler for freight wagons are still to be agreed upon [Railway Gazette 2019].

Another coupler with similar features, the *Voith CargoFlex Hybrid*, has been developed for freight locomotives. The main difference from the *CargoFlex* is its additional compatibility with wagons equipped with UIC-screw couplers [Voith 2018:3].

In the framework of the German research project *Innovativer Güterwagen*, two semi-automated centre buffer coupler systems are being tested, namely a

Scharfenberg type (the *Voith CargoFlex* described above) and a Schwab type. No information is available about upgrade possibilities to an automated coupler for the Schwab type, developed by *Faiveley* [BMVI 2018:16f]. At the time of writing (May 2019), the final report for *Innovativer Güterwagen* had not been published [NEE 2019:20].

Regarding European projects, the S2R project *FR8RAIL* has designed a new automatic coupler along with a migration plan [Bergstrand 2019:38]. However, the documentation and details related to the new device are confidential. The S2R project *FR8RAIL II* is expected to continue the work of *FR8RAIL*, and to deliver a new automatic coupler with electrical and data transmission capabilities at TRL 6 at the least [S2R JU 2018b:63].

The initiative called Competitive Freight Wagon (CFW), focused on developing two competitive freight wagon types, includes in its concept an automated central buffer coupler with a brake pipe connection [Bänsch 2014:25f]. Recently, the design of a concept with a “fully automated central buffer coupler” has been announced [LOK Report 2019].

The TIS has proposed developing a digital automated coupler (DAC). The final stage of the development, called DAC 5, would provide a coupler system – which in addition to the previously presented features would include remote-controlled decoupling [TIS 2019c:42]. However, no specific design seems to be available.

Regarding shunting couplers, there are several commercial solutions available. They all appear to share the same characteristics and enable the automated coupling of wagons as well as automated, remote-controlled uncoupling. However, unlike the automated coupler for wagons, when a brake connection is needed, it must be performed manually [Stuhr 2013:28f]. The table below shows the TRL for different coupling types.

Innovations		Highest TRL
Semi-automated coupler	Manual brake connection	9
	Automated brake connection	9
Automated coupler	Conventional	6
	Digital (DAC)	2
Automated shunting coupler (manual brake connection)		9

Table 9. TRL assessment of coupling systems. Source: Own elaboration

According to the collected information, several semi-automated coupling systems for freight (with automated brake connection and without) have been

developed for commercial use. Regarding automated systems for freight, the highest TRL appears to be achieved by the system developed in FR8RAIL II. The upgrade possibilities offered by Voith CargoFlex are also promising. The DAC system, by contrast, seems to be limited to a concept that requires development.

5.2.2 Automation of brake tests

As explained in section 4.1.4, this process is one of the most time-consuming operations in HYS. The full version must be performed at least once before the departure of the train from the MY. In addition, the simplified version must be performed in the MY under the circumstances explained in section 4.1.4. For these reasons, together with automatic coupling, innovations related to the automation of brake tests in freight trains are highly relevant. They can have an immediate positive impact on the efficiency of shunting processes through saving time.

The full brake test (see section 4.1.4) requires at least three walks: one preliminary walk plus two inspection walks. The preliminary walk includes additional tasks different from the brake test. Therefore, the current plans and experiences for increasing the automation of the brake test mainly focus on avoiding the two inspection walks (semi-automated brake test in this thesis) instead of automating the whole test (automated brake test in this thesis).

Several national initiatives have been launched to enhance the LoA of the brake test. In France, *Traxens* together with *SNCF Logistics* have developed a device to automate the brake test, claiming to be “*the first railway in Europe to implement automated brake testing on commercial freight trains*” [*Railway Gazette 2018a*]. *Traxens* also cooperates with CFL Multimodal to install the *Traxens Box* device on CFL wagons. An initial test was conducted in 2019 [*Dubey 2019*]. The device consists of a box that is wirelessly connected to sensors and which transmits data to the cloud and to other elements of the train. According to the company, the battery-powered device takes only “*a few minutes*” to be installed [*Dubey 2019*]. No additional information seems to be available about how the system operates or which kind of sensors are required and how are they installed. It seems unlikely that the device would enable the full automation of the test without further wagon adaptation.

The implementation of a semi-automated brake test procedure is also part of the *Ein-Personen-Betrieb* strategy of SBB Cargo. SBB Cargo, together with Rail Cargo Group (RCG) and the company PJM have developed a system to automate the process. According to PJM, the “*process completely substitutes the mechanical and visual inspection*” [PJM 2019:2]. The system includes wireless communication with the driver tablet using the LTE standard [Pilz 2018]. According to SBB Cargo, this component was tested in 2019 and is expected to be implemented for regular operations during 2020 [SBB Cargo 2019]. No official information about the system has been released, but other sources [Frei 2018] indicate that the system does not avoid the preliminary inspection. Among others, the brake regime (e.g. G, P) and the valves must still be manually operated.

The S2R project ARCC has been also exploring alternatives for enhancing the LoA of the brake test. To this end, two alternatives are proposed. The first is based on avoiding fitting all the wagons with additional equipment. Instead, additional equipment is required for the locomotives, as well as the installation of hot-wheel detectors on exit routes around MYs to measure the axle temperature and check if the brakes are released or activated. This alternative would enable skipping the two walk inspections in the MY. Additional information about this approach, based on an initiative by Canadian Pacific [Jamieson et al. 2013:1], can be found in [Troche et al. 2018:25f].

The second alternative is similar to the methods developed by Traxens and PMJ. The system architecture proposed in ARCC is depicted in Figure 25. As shown in the figure, this architecture implies installing several components in each wagon, including a sensor showing the position of the brake (applied or released), an on-board unit, monitoring sensors, a device for communicating with the locomotive’s on-board unit, and a power supply.

Figure 25. Architecture of the brake test system proposed in ARCC. Source: [Troche et al. 2018:30]

However, the authors acknowledge that the proposed solution would not substitute for tasks such as the control of the brake components and would mostly be restricted to checking the application and release of the brakes [Troche et al. 2018:29f]. TRL 5 is expected to be reached in the framework of the ARCC project [S2R JU 2016:24].

An interesting possibility for enhancing the automation of brake tests is offered by a “smart” end-of-train device. This device is already in operation in USA. It is installed in the last wagon of the train and provides information about the pressure in the brake pipe. A solar cell provides power supply to the device to transmit the device’s status to the driver [Wingens et al. 2019:26]. No information about the commercial use of this technology in Europe was found. The table below shows the estimated TRLs for the semi-automated and fully automated brake tests.

Innovations		Highest TRL
Brake test	Semi-automated	9
	Full automated	5

Table 10. TRL assessment of automated brake tests Source: Own elaboration

According to the information provided in this chapter, and despite the lack of details, several experiences seem to confirm that the current technology for a semi-automated brake test is already commercially available. In this chapter, two approaches to semi-automated brake tests have been presented. The first approach is based on the axle load and requires checking the brakes outside the MY. This approach does not address the problem of brake malfunction when the train is already in the rail network. The other approach appears either to have been commercialized already (Traxens) or is soon to be commercialized (SBB).

Regarding the fully automated brake test, despite the proposals to use end-of-train devices for brake tests, the adaptation of some mechanisms (such as valves and other wagon elements) to be remote-controlled seems to be far from consolidation. In addition, the preliminary walk is performed together the technical inspection, which would reduce the time savings of a full brake test without parallel progress in this field. According to the collected information, the most promising progress has been made in the ARCC project and the project has determined a TRL 5 goal. Hence, a fully automated brake test has been estimated to have reached TRL 5.

5.2.3 Automation of shunting vehicles

Traditionally, drivers must be inside the locomotive to control the vehicle. However, for several decades the radio control of shunting vehicles has been widespread [VBG 2014:5]. This offers several advantages, such as the possibility of pushing cuts without additional staff, which means the driver can step up to the first wagon and control the locomotive and check the track in front of the cut [VBG 2014:5]. Despite these advantages, automation by radio-controlled locomotives remains limited and largely implies a change in the location of the driver, who still performs the same work.

Several projects are working currently to develop a vehicle for shunting wagons in an automated manner. These research projects can be divided into two categories. The first is focused on the automation of a shunting locomotive and the second is focused on the development of an alternative vehicle.

Figure 26. Classification of shunting vehicles. Source: Own elaboration

Furthermore, experiences and research related to the automation of shunting locomotives can be grouped into two types: *general* shunting locomotives and so-called hump locomotives. The latter are specialized in pushing wagons over the hump in HYs.

Concepts for the development of automated hump locomotives in Germany date back to the 1990s [Mickler 1996]. Once the pushing of cuts over the hump has been automated (see section 4.1.3), the next step entails moving the hump locomotive in an automated manner to the hump.

Recently, a prototype called VAL2020 was developed within the framework of

the project *ZBA 4.0 [Expert#2]*. The prototype focuses on automating the running back of the hump locomotive to the next cut to be shunted over the hump. According to Cichon et al. [*n.d.:2f*], the prototype is equipped with several hardware modules, such as an RGB camera, a thermal camera and a lidar for obstacle detection. The precise position of the locomotive is provided by a differential global navigation satellite system (dGNSS) and a highly precise map of the tracks. In addition, movement orders can be wirelessly transmitted to the locomotive. The collected and received data are processed in a unit located in the locomotive. Subsequently, acceleration and brake instructions (with help of the braking curves of the locomotive) are transmitted to the locomotive steering system.

Project leaders have commented on the satisfactory outputs of the test but have also mentioned the need for further development. Tests of the prototype under poor visibility and research on track detection are planned. A design suitable for mass production is anticipated by 2021 [*LOK Report 2018*].

The technical requirements for an automated general shunting locomotive are more stringent because of the variety of tasks performed. In addition to the equipment described for hump locomotives, extra conditions must be considered in developing this locomotive type [*Expert#2*].

The German project *RANGierASSistent* worked on developing on-board modular assistance for shunting operations with locomotives. This project focused on developing a prototype to support the shunter assistant. The locomotive is fitted with a radar sensor to detect people (already in use in the automobile industry) and a camera to identify the track. The prototype also has a component to calculate the pull load and thus to estimate the braking distance. Collected data are assessed by a unit installed in the locomotive and shown on a display [*Franzen et al. 2017b:8ff*].

SBB Cargo, in the framework of a strategy to increase the automation of shunting, follows a strategy called *ein-Personen-Betrieb*. This strategy consists of developing tools to reduce the number of workers needed for shunting from two to one [*Sonntag 2017:9*]. SBB Cargo is testing two collision warning systems. The first system, developed by *RailVision*, consists of two video cameras which record the area in front of the locomotive within a radius of

70 m. The video signal is processed with software to identify obstacles and the state of the track (e.g. switch position). In addition, the system will identify shunting signals, but this has not yet been integrated into the system. The video is transmitted to the display in the locomotive cab and to the display of a radio-control device used by the shunter worker. In addition to the video transmission, the system alerts the worker in case of danger by acoustic signals and triggers the brake procedure if required.

The second system, developed by *Bosch* for tramways, combines radar sensors and a video camera system to identify the state of the track. The radar identifies obstacles within a radius of 170 m [*Frei 2018*].

Another promising system is the MALS-BM. This Russian project by RZD has developed a driverless system for shunting in MYs. The system consists of a shunting locomotive whose position in the MY is determined by track circuits and dGNSS (GLONASS). In addition, the locomotive can be radio-controlled by the yard operator [*Rozenberg 2017*]. The locomotive is capable of coupling wagons in an automated manner. After the yard operator sets the route and the required parameters [*MALS 2018*], the shunting locomotive – equipped with a laser system – determines the distance to the wagon and reduces its speed to automatically couple the wagon [*unknown 2015*]. This system was tested in 2017; at that time, according to Rozenberg [*2017*], “*more important operations are still performed with the assistance of a driver*”. Further information about the project has not been made available since then.

One of the S2R projects, the project *Smart*, concentrates on developing a prototype for the autonomous detection of obstacles [*SMART n.d.b*]. As shown in Figure 27, the project has mounted a set of commercial sensors composed of a night-vision camera, two stereo cameras, a thermal camera and a 3D laser scanner for mid (up to 200 m) and long-range (up to 1000 m) obstacle detection [*Ristić-Durrant 2019a:5ff*].

Figure 27. System architecture for obstacle detection in project SMART. Source: [Ristić-Durrant 2019a:6]

The collected data are processed by machine learning algorithms, which detect and classify the objects and possible obstacles. The output is a distance estimation and the state of the rail track. However, machine learning algorithms require a large volume of training data. The first set of data was collected in dynamic field tests [Ristić-Durrant 2019b]. It is expected that the system developed in the project will reach, in the best case, TRL 5 [S2R JU 2016:27].

The S2R project ARCC has a work stream dedicated to ATO in freight. However, the demonstrator is focused on mainline transport. The project is oriented towards testing a demonstrator with a GoA2 using a driver cab in which ATO would control the brake and traction. A locomotive with ETCS on-board will be used together with an obstacle-detection system already developed by Bombardier [Kahl 2019]. The amount of information that is publicly available is limited; no information was found regarding testing the system for shunting tasks.

Regarding the development of alternative shunting vehicles, the project led by *DB Systel* in a depot in Paderborn is highly relevant. A road-rail vehicle developed by the company *Zwiehoff* (Rotrac E2) and capable of pulling roughly 250 tonnes has been used. Tests with GPS for positioning and RFID for vehicle identification have been performed. The optical identification of the number of wagons has been also tested [Knapmüller et al. 2018:25ff; *DB Systel* 2017].

The initiative seems to have focused mainly on testing the feasibility of several technologies in a relevant environment, with TRL ranging from 5 to 6. As Knapmöller et al. [2018:26] mentioned, the dispatch system is currently being tested in the follow-up project Aura. This project is further described in section 5.2.5.

The German project *Galileo Online: Go!* addressed a different element of implementing shunting automation on a vast scale, namely the precise positioning of vehicles in a shunting yard. Other initiatives have worked on the precise positioning of rail vehicles, but although they provided the precise position of freight wagons, the time required was excessive [Zweigel et al. 2017:53]. In *Galileo Online: Go!* the position is calculated by processing data from two GNSS systems, namely GPS and Galileo. At the same time, another module calculates the vehicle position using a set of sensors, such as accelerometers. Data transmission is performed by the network protocol called simple object access protocol (SOAP) and LTE.

The tests, performed by an alternative shunting vehicle (E-Maxi L), are performed in a flat-shunted yard in Wustermark. The shunting vehicle and the wagons are equipped with receivers, and the position of the participants is transmitted to a central service where the movement order is generated. Next, the MY manager activates the movement order and coordinates the non-automated activities (coupling, switches and movement instruction).

The precision of the vehicle position achieved an average value of 0.65 m with a speed of around 1 m/s [Zweigel et al. 2018:45ff]. The required energy for the receiver was supplied by batteries installed for this purpose [Zweigel 2018:174]. According to the project team, some technical challenges remain unresolved, such as the energy supply and the miniaturize of the components [Zweigel et al. 2019:202].

The table below shows the estimated TRL for the innovations needed to develop an automated shunting vehicle.

Innovations	Highest TRL
Obstacle recognition	5
Track recognition	6
Shunting vehicle positioning	9
Shunting vehicle communication	9
Automated shunting coupler (manual brake connection)	9

Table 11. TRL assessment of innovations for automated shunting vehicles. Source: Own elaboration

Several initiatives are researching the possibilities offered by the technologies to develop automated shunting vehicles. Both locomotive shunting and alternative vehicles face similar challenges: to recognize and assess the environment and to determine the position of the involved vehicles precisely and rapidly. However, obstacle and track-element recognition technologies already offer interesting results that can be used to assist the shunting staff. On-board hardware can take advantage of the technology developed by the automotive industry. Sensors such as cameras, radars, lidars and infrared are available but require some adaptation for rail particularities.

Currently, the weakest link seems to be the software. Data assessment to identify obstacles using conventional algorithms and technologies derived from AI (artificial intelligence), such as neuronal networks, requires vast data to achieve reliability. Track recognition seems to be slightly more advanced than obstacle recognition due to the more limited possibilities.

Despite the progress, developing technology for shunting vehicles would enable only pull-shunting operations in highly restricted cases, such as hump locomotives. For pushing operations, a similar system should be installed either in the last wagon of the cut or through installing additional hardware in the MY.

Some projects have achieved good results with the positioning of vehicles in MYs through the following combinations: GNSS systems and sensors; dGNSS and detailed representation of the yard; or dGNSS and trackside equipment, such as track circuits. The combination of GLONASS and track circuit is already in commercial operation, but no data could be found regarding system precision. The hump locomotive developed in framework ZBA 4.0 is expected to enter commercial operation in 2021. Therefore, it can cautiously be concluded that this innovation has reached TRL 9.

In the field of communications, the most critical technological issue seems to be the latency of the communication systems, which limits the speed of operation for safety-critical applications. However, because shunting operations are performed at low speeds (25 km/h maximum), latency does not seem to be a critical issue. In addition, 5G technology should be able to reduce the latency [*Rees 2018:70*].

Table 12 presents an assessment of the LoA of current shunting vehicles and a hypothetical shunting vehicle, which would integrate all the available technologies at TRL 9.

Level of Automation	Shunting vehicle	
	Current situation	Current innovation level (TRL 9)
LoA0	X	X
LoA1	X	X
LoA2	X	X
LoA3	-	(X)
LoA4	-	-

Table 12. LoA assessment of automated shunting vehicles. Source: Own elaboration

According to the LoA defined in Chapter 3, it appears that despite the progress to date, current technology does not meet the conditions to enable a generalized upgrade of shunting vehicles from LoA2 to LoA3. However, developments related to automating hump locomotives suggests that the implementation of automated vehicles under human supervision (LoA3) will be achieved soon. Regarding general shunting vehicles, although initiatives such as the MALS system allow some operations to be performed automatically under human supervision, certain operations must be directly performed by a driver. The possibility of an automated general shunting vehicle is not yet a realistic goal.

5.2.4 Automation of freight wagons

Experiences and projects related to automated freight wagons can be divided into two groups. The first consists of projects centred on developing a self-propelled freight wagon that can roll by itself without being coupled to a shunting vehicle. The second group comprises projects which have mainly focused on developing a freight wagon for integration within wider automated processes and which may integrate other relevant components (such as automated coupling or an automated brake test). This second group is labelled in this work as “intelligent wagon”.

Several technologies have been developed in recent decades in relation to the self-propelled freight wagon. One of the most important is the CargoMover. The CargoMover was partially based on the CargoSprinter and was developed in the early 2000s by Siemens and the RWTH Aachen. Although the idea has

not been commercially implemented, CargoMover pioneered the equipping of self-propelled wagons with technologies which are still being tested and improved for locomotive automation. These include laser, radar and cameras for obstacles [Dellmann et al. 2006:237]. Among the current initiatives, the initiative Wagon 4.0 presented a concept for a self-moving wagon [Pfaff et al. 2017:10]. However, this innovation path lost its importance a few years ago [PwC et al. 2015:183]. No mention of self-propelled wagons was found in the documents reviewed in section 5.1.1.

By contrast, the development of technologies to integrate wagons in wider automated processes has good prospects. An early innovative concept related to the intelligent wagon was the CargoSprinter, developed in the late 1990s. CargoSprinter was a freight multiple unit formed by wagons equipped with automated coupling and contactless transmission of data, but was not prepared for automated operation [FIS 2019]. The concept was not commercially successful in Germany [Grotelüschen 2019].

Key issues for the intelligent wagon are the equipment and the technologies required to enable the integration of the wagon in automation processes. Although the common definition of “intelligent wagon” comprises elements to enhance the maintenance [Balog et al. 2018], I focus on the elements with a direct connection to automated shunting. Figure 28 shows the relevant technologies selected.

Figure 28. Technologies for the integration of the automated wagon. Source: Own elaboration

Automated coupling and automated brake tests have already been addressed in this chapter. Positioning has been discussed in relation to automated shunting vehicles but is commented on here too. Other topics have been superficially mentioned, such as communication and sources of energy. In this section, information about experiences and projects related to technologies which have not been addressed is introduced. In addition, a general overview of an intelligent wagon is provided. This section does not provide a comprehensive overview of each technology but rather presents the technological possibilities and commercial applications – if any – in rail freight transport.

Wagon positioning and the related equipment is not a new topic. However, until recently wagons were equipped with GPS mainly to provide logistic services and thus to know the position of the wagon in the rail network [VTG *n.d.*]. This is an important point because of the precision required for shunting, where the acceptable error is measured in centimetres rather than metres. High precision is required to locate the wagon in a specific train and to determine the order of the wagon within a cut [Willems 2015:5]. Among shunting vehicles, the wagons are usually stationary, resulting in highly accurate location of the wagon using GNSS positioning systems [Anquela *et al.* 2013:1].

Several initiatives focus on wagon positioning for shunting applications. The German project *EVIPOS* aims to develop software for precise positioning of rail wagons by combining different positioning systems, such as GNSS, local networks and Bluetooth. The project includes several tests to analyse the suitability of the technology [BMBF *n.d.*:2; *EVIPO n.d.*]. The development of this innovation seems similar to that of shunting vehicle positioning. Although the available information focuses on GNSS systems, combination technologies such as that used for shunting vehicles might also be possible. Although the technical requirements seem less demanding than for shunting vehicles, no commercial use of precise wagon positioning was found.

Wagon identification has been researched and applied in trains for several decades [French 2008]. The most common technology used to date is radio-frequency identification (RFID). The device consists of an RFID-transponder

(usually passive) fitted in the vehicle, which is identified by an RFID-reader. The RFID-transponder is equipped with an antenna which transmits the information to the RFID-reader. High frequency (HF) systems enable a read distance of up to 30 cm. Ultra-high frequency (UHF) systems, which are the most widely used, enable read distances of up to several meters [Rees 2018:74f].

In the freight rail sector in Europe, SBB Cargo started fitting freight cars with UHF tags and installing wayside readers at the entrance and exit of rail freight yards in 2016 [Swedberg 2016:1f]. Additional information about wagon identification is presented in Section 5.2.5, which deals with the automation of the yard operation.

Sensors for process automation usually require electric power, including the sensors used in automated brake tests, communication devices and GNSS receivers. Hence, power supply is a central element for the intelligent wagon. The two alternatives for providing freight wagons with a power supply are, first, a power line connected to the locomotive; and second, installing a harvesting device plus a battery in each wagon. The second option allows the produced energy to be stored for later use.

Power lines are the default option for passenger trains, but they have not been implanted in freight trains at a large scale. In the project *Innovative Güterwagen*, power was transmitted by a power line. This connection, however, was not integrated in the coupler and had to be manually connected [BMVI 2018:26]. It is important to note that although a power line is not indispensable for automated shunting, it is essential for another relevant feature in rail freight transport: the electro-pneumatic brake [TIS 2019c:35].

Energy harvesting seems to be the most successful option so far. VTG has installed a module developed by *railCare* in refrigerated wagons. An hydraulic pump installed in the wheelset produces energy due to vibration when train speed exceeds 30 km/h and this energy is stored in batteries [VTG 2019]. A possible problem in this system relates to storing enough energy if a wagon remains idle, such as in a MY. Another possibility for energy harvesting, which is used in commercial operations for vehicle tracking, entails installing solar cells in wagons [Ulianov 2018:21; VTG n.d.:2].

The SBB 5L project is testing a harvesting system to power an automated brake test [Railway Gazette 2019]. The system includes generators mounted on the bearings and a battery. The generators produce energy starting at 20 km/h [Frei 2018]. The initiative Wagon 4.0 proposes installing wheelset generators and batteries for a power supply which would provide sufficient energy for all sensors [Pfaff et al. 2017:6]. Despite the considerations and information reviewed, no commercial experience has proven that energy harvesting could produce enough energy to power all sensors in a wagon reliably.

The main discussion regarding wagon communication focuses on wireless communication or the use of cables. The advantages related to reliability, latency, safety, and energy consumption offered by a wired connection are clear [Enning et al. 2017a:4]. However, wireless communication opens a vast field of possibilities. As already mentioned, the project *Innovative Güterwagen* has used a data bus cable to connect wagons with the locomotive. As with the power cable, the data bus was not integrated in the coupler and had to be manually connected [BMVI 2018:26]. The initiative Wagon 4.0 proposes installing a CAN bus for communication between the elements of the wagon and 3G/5G wireless technology for external communication with the human operator [Pfaff et al. 2017:6].

The S2R project FR8RAIL, in the framework of research on the design of an intelligent wagon focused on preventive maintenance, is exploring a wireless alternative for data transmission between wagons [FR8RAIL n.d.]. The development appears to be still in a conceptual phase [Funke 2017:29]. Table 13 shows the estimated TRL for innovations needed for the development of an intelligent freight wagon.

Innovations		Highest TRL
Wagon positioning		9
Power supply	Harvesting	7
	Power line	9
Wagon communication	Wireless	7
	Communication line	9
Wagon identification (RFID)		9
Semi-automated coupler	Manual brake connection	9
	Automated brake connection	9
Automated coupler	Conventional	6
	Digital (DAC)	2-3
Brake test	Semi-automated	9
	Full automated	5

Table 13. TRL assessment of key technologies for the intelligent freight wagon. Source: Own elaboration

The conventional freight wagon has two main weaknesses in comparison with shunting vehicles. First, the lack of energy supply hinders the implementation of several key innovations. GNSS receivers, which are essential for wagon positioning, and sensors for the semi-automated brake test both need a power source. Second, the screw coupler is labour-intensive and hinders the easy implementation of commercial solutions for the energy supply – such as a power line. The screw coupler also obstructs the required communication regarding certain processes, such as the brake test, for the locomotive or for MY staff.

An additional issue is the integration of existing technologies. As discussed in this section, many technologies for the intelligent wagon are already available in the market. However, there is no standard for data exchange and there are compatibility issues between devices. These challenges have negative consequences for the integration of devices manufactured for different purposes. Although some work has been done in this area, such as the creation of the Industry Platform for Telematics and Sensor Technology (ITSS) [TIS 2019c:14ff], much remains to be resolved.

In addition to the technologies already discussed in relation to brake tests and coupling systems, several other technologies could be applied. Energy could be supplied by the locomotive through a power line, enabling the implementation of the semi-automated brake test, and enabling wagon positioning when connected to the mainline locomotive. Idle wagons in an HY would require harvesting methods to power the sensors. Communication could be performed by a data bus, enabling transmission of the test result to the locomotive driver. (Similarly for the idle wagons as the power supply, information transmission must be wireless in this case). However, without a coupler system that is able to automate the connection of these lines, the time and cost required to handle wagons in the MY would increase significantly.

The assessment of the LoA of the current freight wagon, compared with a hypothetical freight wagon which would integrate all the available technologies at TRL 9, is presented in the table below.

Level of Automation	Freight wagon	
	Current situation	Current innovation level (TRL 9)
LoA0	X	X
LoA1	X	X
LoA2	X	X
LoA3	-	-
LoA4	-	-

Table 14. LoA assessment for the automated freight wagon. Source: Own elaboration.

According to the LoA defined in Chapter 3, it can be concluded that despite the progress made so far, the current technology does not meet the conditions to move from LoA2 to LoA3. The implementation of TRL 9 innovations would yield time savings but would not be enough to effectively integrate the wagon in automated processes that merely require human supervision.

5.2.5 Automation of the yard operation

Thus far, I have discussed innovations and technologies to increase automation in wagons and locomotives. However, to achieve LoA close to full automation, yard operation must be upgraded as well. This section presents initiatives focused on automating the rail operation and planning. In addition, key technologies and innovations for MY automation that were not addressed in previous chapters are discussed here. The section is divided into the three areas shown in Figure 29.

Figure 29. Innovation groups in MY operation. Source: Own elaboration

Operation of MYs is traditionally performed based on the available information and the experience of the MY operator [Trafikverket 2018:47]. Certain initiatives are already exploring possibilities to increase the automation of the process.

The S2R project OptiYard aims to improve the information of the yard operator and hence to move towards automating the operative planning of the MY. The project is developing a software module that simulates the operation of the MY and the surrounding network in real-time; the simulation data are used to optimize the operations in the MY. The output of the optimization will support the MY operator in rescheduling operations and other operative decisions. The optimization module should achieve TRL 4 [Lutz 2017:2ff].

The S2R project ARCC also includes the research of real-time yard management in MY. However, the output of the project seems to be limited to defining requirements and processes within an MY and analysing the interactions and information flows between stakeholders [ARCC n.d.]. The activities performed should reach, in the best case, TRL 5 [S2R JU 2016:24].

The S2R project SMART is developing a web-based information system to provide an overview of operations in the MY for the planning of operations [SMART n.d.b:2]. The objective is to provide the MY operator with a tool to support the responsible person in rescheduling tasks in case of timetable deviations of inbound trains. The system gathers information from different IT applications and includes an optimization module [Ristić-Durrant et al. 2018:34ff]. The optimization module is based on a combination of rule-based algorithms and AI with neuronal networks [Ristić-Durrant 2019b]. According to the call of the project, the development of the tool will reach, in the best case, TRL 5 [S2R JU 2016:27]

Regarding German projects, *AuRa* is testing architecture to control an electric shunting vehicle in a flat-shunted facility. The centralized system prepares and dispatches the movement command to the vehicle, and connects with the interlocking system to set the route by switching points and activating the signalling system. After the route is set, the shunting vehicle moves to its destination. The main obstacles to the full automation of MY operations are, first, the installation of sensors on the landside to enable push operations [Knapmüller et al. 2018:27]; and second, the electrification of points to remotely operate them [Fessler et al. 2019:65]. The project is expected to enable the control and operation of several shunting vehicles at the same time. Obstacle and wagon recognition are the most complex elements for the

automation of the MY operations [Expert#1].

Another German project, *Rang-E*, has been also analysing the possibilities for automated operation in flat-shunted yards. The project deals with the feasibility of implementing innovations for shunting automation in a flat-shunted yard [ISL 2017]. The feasibility study explores, among others, the implementation of a system to optimize the shunting operations and the use of autonomous shunting locomotives [Krämer et al. 2017:27]. However, no test or field test will be performed in the Rang-E project [Schwiegershausen 2017:22].

The ZBA 4.0. project plans to develop tools to improve the digital operation and monitoring of HY processes [DB n.d.]. The project aims at designing the future MY with a high degree of automation. The project includes, among others, the real-time operation of the HY, the automation of points, the implementation of paperless process, and the implementation of an automated gate to collect data automatically from inbound trains [DB n.d.]. No additional information about this project has been published.

If we focus on innovative equipment for HY operation, the most promising topic is automated gate operation. The S2R project FR8HUB is working on an intelligent video gate (IVG), mainly focused on an intermodal terminal, to reduce the inspection and check-in times in arrival yards of MYs. The device includes a set of elements and technologies such as cameras, illuminators, RFID, scanners and wheel sensors [Lengu 2018:3]. Wheel sensors would identify when a wagon is approaching. This information would warn the identification system to calibrate the system and capture wagon images when the wagon passes the gate door. The system will be equipped with an RFID reader to identify the RFID tags fitted in the vehicles. Optical character recognition (OCR) software will identify the numbers from the images taken by cameras. A 3D recreation of the wagon obtained by a laser scanner will be used to cross-check the outputs of the OCR software [Lengu 2018:46].

The above idea is not new, and a similar system has been already tested. SBB installed a camera system close to MY Limmattal to identify wagon codes with a combination of image-recognition software and RFID tags. Among other interesting possibilities, the system could identify the order of wagons as well

as damaged wagons [Thalmann n.d.:113ff]. Innovations developed in FR8HUB related to IVG are expected to achieve TRL 6, providing a validated prototype [S2R JU 2017:55].

A further field explored in this thesis are the possibilities offered by the ETCS for shunting. Taking ETCS as the basis for ATO (“ETCS over ATO”) seems to be the horizon for train automation [Siemens 2016b:1ff]. However, this practice has not been extended to the automation of shunting operations as all initiatives analysed in this thesis have been performed under other signalling and control systems.

According to the information obtained, the implementation of ETCS in MYs for shunting operations seems highly unlikely in the short term [Expert#1; Expert#2]. However, steps are being taken to test ETCS in shunting. SBB Cargo claims to be the first European operator to perform shunting operations under ETCS-2 in a siding [SBB Cargo 2015]. In addition, some regulations – such as *RiL 408* – are being adapted in Germany for the use of ETCS in shunting [RiL 408, revised 3]. The table below shows the estimated TRL for the innovations needed for automated operation of an MY.

Innovations		Highest TRL
Vehicle identification	RFID	9
	OCR	6
Automated yard operation		5
Gate scanners		6

Table 15. TRL assessment of technologies for automated yard operation. Source: Own elaboration

Regarding vehicle identification, the OCR system incurs some disadvantages compared with RFID. As for other technologies already discussed, recognition software presents problems that diminish its reliability. Its high complexity means that automated planning operations are currently conceived of as supporting the yard operator to make decisions about the shunting operations rather than providing a whole automated system. The automated operation and coordination of the actors involved is also an early step towards a higher degree of automation. The coordination between vehicles and automated dispatching has been validated with a prototype but further steps are needed before it can be applied commercially.

The IVG requires certain technologies to work together, such as OCR, RFID and a gate scanner, to provide robust information to the yard operator about

inbound trains. Although a prototype is planned for development, the IVG innovation seems promising because it can be implemented in a modular way, progressively including mature technologies.

Table 16 presents an assessment of the LoA of the current MY operation and a hypothetical MY which would integrate all the available technologies at TRL 9.

Level of Automation	MY operation	
	Current situation	Current innovation level (TRL 9)
LoA0	X	X
LoA1	X	X
LoA2	X	X
LoA3	-	-
LoA4	-	-

Table 16. LoA assessment for automated yard operation. Source: Own elaboration

As with the previous cases, an increase in the LoA of the MY cannot be achieved with the commercially available technologies. Indeed, the change from LoA2 to LoA3 appears even more distant here than in the previous sections. This is because of the high complexity of the yard operations that would need to be automated, with only supervision by humans.

5.3 Chapter summary

This section summarizes the innovations analysed in this chapter. In addition, the LoA of the three elements classified is analysed. The table below shows the lists the innovations according to their maximum TRL.

Innovations	Highest TRL
Shunting vehicle positioning	9
Shunting vehicle communication	9
Automated shunting coupler with manual brake connection	9
Wagon positioning	9
Power supply with power line	9
Wagon communication with communication line	9
Semiautomated coupler with manual brake connection	9
Semiautomated coupler with automated brake connection	9
Vehicle identification with RFID	9
Semiautomated brake test	9
Power supply with harvesting	7
Wireless wagon communication	7
Track recognition	6
Vehicle identification with OCR	6
Conventional automated coupler	6
Gate scanners	6
Obstacle recognition	5
Full automated brake test	5
Automated yard operation	5
Digital automated coupler (DAC)	2

Table 17. Summary of innovations classified according to their TRL. Source: Own elaboration

As shown in Table 17, most innovations have reached a relatively high TRL. Despite some uncertainties due to the lack of accurate data or the complex mapping process for the different innovations, roughly half of the analysed innovations have reached technological maturity (TRL 9).

The implementation of certain innovations has been technically possible for several decades already. Examples are the power supply with a power line for freight wagons and the semi-automated coupler. Others, however, are relatively new, such as vehicle positioning. The latter is especially interesting because several combinations of technologies with different degrees of technological maturity have been presented. The various combinations are feasible for diverse tasks and all of them involve GNSS technology.

Certain technologies are being used for other applications, such as harvesting methods for generating electricity for logistics applications. However, it is unclear whether they could provide enough energy in a reliable way to power all sensors and communication devices. Especially critical could be situations such as those common in HYs, where wagons remain idle for days in the classification yards.

Table 18 shows the LoA of the elements considered, namely shunting vehicles, freight wagons and MY operation. The table reflects the current situation compared with the added implementation of TRL 9 innovations.

Level of Automation	Shunting vehicle		Freight wagon		MY operation	
	Current situation	Current innovation level (TRL9)	Current situation	Current innovation level (TRL9)	Current situation	Current innovation level (TRL9)
LoA0	X	X	X	X	X	X
LoA1	X	X	X	X	X	X
LoA2	X	X	X	X	X	X
LoA3	-	(X)	-	-	-	-
LoA4	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 18. Summary of LoA evolution. Source: Own elaboration

Table 18 shows that there are few changes in the LoA for any of the elements considered. The most significant change would occur for the shunting vehicles through the possible LoA3 automation of hump locomotives. The other two elements remain at LoA2 and are not close to progressing to LoA3.

Of interest, however, is the discussion about increasing the automation by integrating several processes, as outlined in section 3.4. This scenario would apply, for instance, in the implementation of semi-automated brake tests. Several tasks which are usually done separately would be performed together by pressing a button.

6 Application case

This chapter is divided into two main sections. In the first section, three scenarios with different degrees of LoA and TRL are defined. For each of the three scenarios, the shunting processes of two generic trains (inbound and outbound) in an HY are described. The second part comprises an evaluation of the three scenarios, highlighting the time savings derived from implementing various sets of innovations. To conclude, an estimation of the saving in labour costs for each scenario is provided. The objective of this chapter is twofold:

1. To illustrate the possibilities offered by the innovations explored or tested to date in the field of freight rail shunting.
2. To provide the basis for a quantitative assessment of the advantages that implementing these technological innovations might yield.

6.1 Scenarios

This section defines the three scenarios with different LoAs and TRLs. Each scenario depicts the shunting processes of a generic inbound train and a generic outbound. As mentioned in Section 4.1.2, the train used as a reference for both cases (inbound and outbound) is a 524-m train, which includes the locomotive and 23 wagons. The 23 wagons are distributed in 16 cuts.

Although not explicitly stated, the definition of scenarios aims at correlation with several time horizons. As shown in Figure 30, Scenario 1 corresponds to the current operation of the HY described in Chapter 4. Scenario 2 is defined as an HY where technologically mature innovations have been implemented and is considered here as a mid-term horizon. Finally, Scenario 3 (long-term horizon) is defined as an HY where all innovations required for LoA4 operation have been developed and implemented.

Figure 30. Definition of automation scenarios. Source: Own elaboration

The scenarios are defined incrementally, allowing the addition of innovations to the previous scenarios (which have less automation). This progressive deployment would enable the gradual adoption of innovations without requiring a completely new design of the HY.

6.1.1 Scenario 1. Status quo

This scenario is based on the process description provided in Chapter 4. It describes the state-of-the-art of the shunting processes performed in a generic German HY that has automated hump operation. The following paragraphs provide a condensed version of the shunting processes described in previous chapters.

After receiving authorisation from the HY operator to enter the facility and to be assigned a track in the arrival yard, the inbound train enters the HY. Once the train reaches its track, the main locomotive is manually uncoupled. Then a shunting route is assigned, and the main locomotive moves away. During this process, the HY staff begin the technical inspection of the inbound train. The information previously received about the train is checked and compared with the actual train. Among other things, the train is inspected for damaged wagons and the order of the wagons is checked. The inspection includes the preparation of documentation for humping, which is digitally transmitted to staff responsible for humping. If a wagon is damaged or cannot be humped, it is flat-shunted to the proper yard location.

The next step consists of preparing the inbound train for humping. The staff uncouple and disconnect the brake pipe for the cuts specified in the

documentation that was transmitted digitally. Once this task is finished, the hump locomotive starts pushing the cuts over the hump and the hump roll, down to the classification yard. Here, a close-up device brings the wagon closer to the next wagon.

Once the train is complete or its scheduled time of departure is close, the preparations start. The shunting locomotive arrives and compresses the wagons. Then, the HY staff couple the cuts and connect the brake pipe. Once this process is complete, the shunting locomotive pulls the composition to the departure yard. The shunting locomotive is uncoupled and moves away and is replaced by the mainline locomotive.

The train and wagon inspection then begin together with the preliminary walk for the brake test (pre-inspection). Once this process finishes, the second part of the brake test begins. The outbound train is then ready for departure. After the staff place the end-of-train signal and the train is dispatched by the yard operator, the train leaves the HY. The figure below shows the times required for the processes previously described for the two generic inbound and outbound freight trains.

Figure 31. Process time: assessment for Scenario 1. Source: Own elaboration.

According to the assessment reported in Chapter 4, the total time required for handling both trains, without counting the idle time, is 162 min. Of this, 60 min (37%) is required for tasks and processes related to manually coupling and uncoupling trains. The total time needed for inspection tasks (inspection of the inbound train, and technical inspection and brake test for the outbound train)

is 68 minutes (42% of the total handling time). The remaining time is mainly spent on locomotive shunting.

The times dedicated to the handling of inbound trains are shown in blue in Figure 31; times for the hump process are shown in green, and times for outbound train preparation are shown in orange. It is evident that most of the time (60%) is spent on processes related to preparing the outbound train.

6.1.2 Scenario 2. Implementation of TRL 9 innovations

This section includes a description of a possible sequence for the shunting process in a highly automated MY, if the TRL 9 innovations analysed in Chapter 5 are implemented. In addition, in a similar manner to that of the previous section, the required time for all operations involved in the entire process is evaluated. Table XX shows a summary of the TRL 9 innovations mapped in the previous chapter.

Innovations	Highest TRL
Shunting vehicle positioning	9
Shunting vehicle communication	9
Automated shunting coupler with manual brake connection	9
Wagon positioning	9
Power supply with power line	9
Wagon communication with communication line	9
Semiautomated coupler with manual brake connection	9
Semiautomated coupler with automated brake connection	9
Vehicle identification with RFID	9
Semiautomated brake test	9

Table 19. Innovations with TRL 9. Source: Own elaboration

In the following paragraphs, a TRL 9 scenario is described. The modifications related to the previous scenario are written in italics.

After receiving authorisation from the HY operator to enter the facility and to be assigned a track in the arrival yard, the inbound train *equipped with semi-automated couplers* enters the HY. *The wagons, equipped with RFID, are digitally checked by a trackside reader and the collected information is compared with the information received from the IM.* Once the train reaches its track, the main locomotive is manually uncoupled. Then a shunting route is assigned, and the main locomotive moves away. While this process is taking place, the HY staff have started the technical inspection of the inbound train.

The information previously received about the inbound train is checked and compared with the actual train. Because *the RFID reader has checked the train's order, destination and type of load, the staff focus on searching for damaged wagons.* This inspection includes preparation of the documentation for humping, which is digitally transmitted to the staff responsible for humping. If a wagon is damaged or cannot be humped, it is flat-shunted to the proper yard location.

The next step consists of preparing the inbound train for humping. The staff uncouple and disconnect the brake pipe for the cuts specified in the documentation that was transmitted digitally. Once this task is complete, the hump locomotive starts pushing the cuts over the hump and the hump roll, down to the classification yard. Here, a close-up device brings the wagon closer to the next wagon *and it is automatically coupled to the next wagon, including its brake pipe.*

Once the train is complete or its scheduled time of departure is close, the preparations start. The shunting locomotive arrives and pulls the composition to the departure yard. The shunting locomotive is remotely uncoupled and moves away, and it is substituted by the mainline locomotive. Next, the train and wagon inspection starts, together with the preliminary walk for the brake test (pre-inspection). Once this process is finished, the second part of the brake test begins. The outbound train is then ready for departure. After the staff place the end-of-train signal and the train is dispatched by the yard operator, the train leaves the HY.

The innovation *power supply with power line* is not included in the above scenario. Although this innovation would enable the implementation of the semi-automated brake test, the need to manually connect and disconnect the power line would outweigh the time savings derived from the semi-automated brake test. The time required to connect the power line is critical if the coupling of wagons is to be automated, because such a connection implies a walk exclusively for this purpose. The figure below shows the times required for the processes described for two generic inbound and outbound freight trains.

Figure 32. Process time: assessment for Scenario 2. Source: Own elaboration.

Technical inspection times were based on DB Cargo [2017:36], which assumes one minute for each wagon. Considering that some of the information is collected by the RFID reader and the main task of the staff is checking for damage, the time for a wagon is estimated at 30 sec. The total time for the 12 wagons is 12 min.

Although the coupling is not automated, one of the advantages of semi-automated coupling is the ease of uncoupling in comparison with using a screw coupler. The uncoupling is performed by pulling a mechanism [Bahnonline.ch 2019], which also results in saving time for the wagon uncoupling. The uncoupling time, in relation to the screw coupler, is cut by three quarters (from 40 to 10 sec); the total time for 15 couplers, with a walk speed of 0.8 m/s, is 12 min.

In summary, after implementing the semi-automated brake coupling and the RFID system, the total time required for handling both trains is 104 min. This reduction is possible due to the time savings on the technical inspection of inbound trains as well as the coupling and uncoupling process.

The difficulties in implementing a semi-automated-brake train with restricted access to power energy was discussed in Section 5.3. If this difficulty can be overcome, an enhanced version of this scenario – with the implementation of a semi-automated brake test – would reduce the time of the brake test from 30 to 5 sec. (Despite avoiding the need for two walks, time would be still required to fill and empty the brake pipe.) Including this innovation, the total time for

handling both trains would be 79 sec.

6.1.3 Scenario 3. Implementation of innovations at LoA4

The previous section explored what can be achieved with the existing technology (TRL 9). This section describes a highly automated scenario. This scenario only includes innovations listed in Section 5.3 and assumes that the configuration of the HY remains the same (arrival, hump, classification yard and departure yard). Innovations that yield marginal time savings in the processes described in the previous sections are not mentioned. The modifications related to the previous scenario are highlighted in italics.

After receiving authorisation from the *HY automated operator system* to enter the facility and to be assigned a track in the arrival yard, the inbound train equipped with *digital automated couplers (DAC)* enters the HY. The wagons, equipped with *RFID, harvesting devices and a set of GNSS receivers*, are digitally checked by an *IVG that includes RFID, OCR and gate scanners*. The collected information is compared with the information received from the IM. *In addition, the scanner analyses the inbound train for damaged wagons.* Once the train reaches its track, the main locomotive is *remotely* uncoupled. Then a shunting route is assigned *by the HY automated operator system*, and the main locomotive moves away. The information previously received about the inbound train is *automatically* checked and compared with the actual train, and *the humping documentation is prepared according to an optimized HY scenario*. If a wagon is damaged or cannot be humped, *the wagon is positioned and automatically* flat-shunted to the proper yard location *by an automated shunting vehicle*.

The next step consists of preparing the inbound train for humping. The *HY automated operator system wirelessly sends the order to the DAC which must be uncoupled for humping. The data bus line, power line and brake pipe, which are integrated in the DAC, automatically disconnect*. Once this task is complete, the *automated* hump locomotive starts pushing the cuts over the hump and the hump roll, down to the classification yard, where a close-up device brings the wagon closer to the next wagon. The wagon is automatically coupled to the next wagon, including its brake pipe, *the data bus line and the power line*.

Once the train is complete or its scheduled time of departure is close, the preparations start. The *automated* shunting locomotive arrives and pulls the composition to the departure yard. The *outbound train runs through an IVG that checks the wagon order and the technical state of the wagon*. The shunting locomotive is remotely uncoupled and moves away and is substituted by the mainline locomotive. Next, the *HY automated operator system remotely adjusts the braking regime, the load set and the state of the brakes*. Once this process finishes, the second part of the brake test, *remotely controlled by the HY automated operator system*, begins. The outbound train is then ready for departure. After the *end-of-train device is remotely activated* and train is dispatched by the *HY automated operator system*, the train leaves the HY. The figure below shows the times required for the processes described for two generic inbound and outbound freight trains.

Figure 33. Process time: assessment for Scenario 3. Source: Own elaboration.

Process times shown in Figure 33 are considerably reduced relative to the previous scenarios. Because of the remote control via wireless or data bus of the DAC couplers, the coupling and uncoupling are almost instant. A similar situation occurs with the train inspections. The IVG enables checking all wagon parameters (wagon order, load, destination and origin) by means of RFID and OCR technology. In addition, the use of scanners enables checking the wagons for damage. Lastly, the introduction of fully automated brake tests avoids the need for three walks (one pre-inspection plus two brake-test walks). However, some time is needed to fill and empty the brake pipe, estimated here as 5 min.

In summary, after the implementation of all technologies mapped in this thesis, the total time required for handling both trains is 46 min. This reduction is possible due to implementing the full automation of all coupling and uncoupling processes as well as the full brake test, and introducing IVG to monitor the state of the wagons.

6.2 Evaluation of scenarios

The implementation of existing commercial solutions can yield substantial time savings in the wagon-handling process in HYs. The figure below summarizes the three main scenarios described in this chapter. It includes Scenario 2 but with the semi-automated brake test being implemented (Scenario 2+).

Figure 34. Summary of process time assessment for all the scenarios. Source: Own elaboration.

Figure 34 shows that implementation of the available commercial technologies in the HY would reduce the handling time by 36%. The additional installation of a semi-automated brake test in the wagons and the required power supply would reduce by half the time required to handle the inbound and outbound train in relation to the current scenario. The scenario where all the mapped innovations are implemented would lead to a time reduction of 72% relative to the current scenario.

The positive impact on handling time of introducing a semi-automated coupling system is clear. Apart from the advantages derived from the automated coupling of wagons, this device would also reduce the uncoupling times. The same is true for time savings due to implementing an RFID system, which would avoid – for instance – having to check the wagon order of the inbound train.

It is important to note that increased automation strongly affects processes which involve staff walking along the train to perform a task. This is key for time savings due to increased automation of the coupling system, but it also occurs through automation of the braking test, by avoiding two or three walks depending on the level of automation. This issue is even more relevant considering that the train considered was only 500 m long, which is shorter than the more cost-effective 750-m freight trains and far from the desired 1000-m freight train [BMVI 2017:14]. These lengths have a strong negative impact on the time required for handling wagons in the HY if no innovations to avoid staff walks are implemented.

Processes that already have a high level of automation, such as those related to hump operations (excluding humping preparations) would not benefit from HY automation to the same degree. The reason is simple: hump processes have achieved already a high level of automation, and further HY automation in facilities with automated humping would yield only marginal time savings.

The time savings through the automation discussed in this chapter enable estimating the order of magnitude of the cost savings due to reduced labour hours. The HY was taken as a reference. If we consider that the HY Mannheim can handle 5600 wagons per day [Rees 2017:23] and they are distributed in a similar manner to the generic train selected for this thesis (23 wagons and 16 cuts), this equates to 243 trains to be handled per day. This figure represents around 85,000 trains handled per year.

The collective labour agreement between the trade union EVG and DB Services GmbH for activities related to shunting operations in freight transport shows an annual salary for shunting workers ranging between €45,000 and €30,000 (salary groups 206 to 210 and excluding group managers) [EVG 2018:64]. Salary varies depending on the salary group and the worker's seniority. To

calculate the order of magnitude of labour savings, an average salary of €35,000 per year was considered. Adding up the German employee on-cost of 20% of the annual gross salary [EUROSTAT 2018c:3], the total is €42,000 per year. Based on the norm of 160 working hours per month, the average hourly salary is around €22. Table 20 shows the order of magnitude of the labour costs related to the wagon-handling time with the automated scenarios defined.

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 2+	Scenario 3
Total minutes/train	162	104	79	46
Total handling time/year (min)	13,770,000	8,840,000	6,715,000	3,910,000
Estimated labour costs (€/year)	5,020,313	3,222,917	2,448,177	1,425,521

Table 20. Order of magnitude of the labour costs. Source: Own elaboration

For the cost calculation, I optimistically assumed that only one worker is needed for each operation. Under these circumstances, the labour cost savings for Scenario 2 are around €1.8 million. For Scenario 2+ the savings would amount to around €2.5 million. Scenario 3 would reduce the labour costs by around €3.5 million relative to Scenario 1.

It is important to highlight that these amounts are merely estimates and a more detailed analysis is necessary. In relation to cost saving, automation may lead to fewer shunting locomotives being required [Krämer 2019:7] as well as energy savings or an increase in capacity of the HY [Siemens 2016a:7], among others.

7 Conclusions and outlook

The results indicate that introducing relatively few commercially available innovations may lead to significant reduction of the shunting-process time in an HY. The assessment demonstrated that implementing a semi-automated coupler or RFID tags could reduce the overall process time by around a third, compared with the current status quo for an HY with automated hump operation. The additional introduction of a semi-automated brake test could almost halve the process times. A scenario in which the automation level is close to providing an autonomous operation, with many innovations (at different stages of development) being implemented, could reduce the processing time by up to three-quarters of the time currently needed in an HY. The time savings derived from implementing innovations in an HY would have less impact on the overall time spent if there is no reduction in idle times of wagons in the HY. The automation of the HY, in turn, has little effect on the reduction of idle times if coordination between HY and IM is lacking. A critical step forward would be achieved by implementing innovations at the IM side. Smooth and continuous transmission of information (e.g. ETA and ETD) between HY and IM is essential to reduce the idle time of wagons and to optimize the yard operations.

It has been shown that automation would produce cost savings, derived from labour-cost savings, of at least €1.8 million per year for a German HY with intense traffic. Further analysis is required to quantify the economic benefits of the time savings due to HY automation more precisely.

Time savings due to process automation has the greatest influence in processes that involve staff walking, such as technical inspections, coupling and uncoupling operations, and brake tests. In these cases, implementing innovations which avoid walks – such as the semi-automated coupler – would yield immediate benefits. By contrast, increasing the automation in an HY would have a modest impact in terms of time savings for processes in which the LoA is already high, such as most hump-related operations.

Time savings associated with implementing innovations and cost reduction from labour productivity increments should foster a modal shift. However, beyond cost competition, service reliability is a key element for the success of

the freight rail sector. Therefore, automation should also improve the robustness of shunting operations. To this end, a back-up system in case of hazard is necessary. This area could pose a severe weakness if not addressed before higher levels of automation are implemented.

Some innovations play a key role by functioning as an enabler for implementing other innovations. An example is the power supply of wagons. The power supply would enable equipping freight wagons with additional equipment to foster shunting automation, such as GNSS receivers or an automated (or semi-automated) brake test. A similar case occurs with (semi-) automated coupling that would enable the cost-efficient connection of a power line and data bus. A key issue in shunting automation is the promotion of compatibility between similar or complementary devices. This affects the different sensors and the communication between them, but can also extend to other innovations, such as (semi-) automated coupling systems.

The automation of whole MYs, whether hump or flat-shunted yards, at Lo3 or higher seems impossible in the medium term and uncertain for the long term. The complexity and variety of tasks and processes performed in an MY hinders the automation of all shunting-related operations. However, the automation at Lo3 of sets of tasks has been already achieved, including humping automation. Integrating further tasks into these highly automated processes may be an effective strategy to increase the LoA of MYs.

There are a few innovations for which several technologies or approaches are being researched or tested. A well-known case is positioning technologies. The use of GNSS techniques is combined with trackside infrastructure (e.g. track circuits), additional sensors (e.g. accelerometers) or digital MY models. Although these technologies might not be technically incompatible, opting for one approach may lead to a path-dependent development of the automation for economic reasons.

The development and implementation of certain sets of innovations may lead to a shift in preference for specific types of freight yards. The improvement of key technologies that enable the development of automated shunting vehicles, such as those required for obstacle recognition, would improve the position of flat-shunted yards versus hump yards. The cost reduction of flat shunting

would play an important role here.

Half of the 20 innovations analysed had achieved TRL 9 and were commercially available at the time of writing. Several of the remaining innovations have also achieved high TRL values. However, it is not likely that all TRL 9 innovations will be implemented soon.

The adoption of technologies and innovations from other sectors, typically the automobile sector, fosters the automation of train shunting. However, adaptation of the technologies is required. This is especially relevant for software recognition techniques, where differences between the two modes of transport play a central role. Such differences include vehicle weight, brake properties and the transport environment.

The automation system analysed in this work comprises only problem detection, namely brake failure or damaged wagons, but not correction. For a highly automated MY, automated correction systems should also be developed.

A key issue in this thesis has been discovering what the concept of automation meant in each document reviewed. The LoA classification developed in this thesis has limited usefulness for classifying the innovations reviewed. However, the discussion about automation in freight yards requires a framework beyond the dichotomy of “non-automated versus automated” that could be used in a broad context.

The incentives of various stakeholders in the operation of the facility may hamper the implementation of innovations in MYs. The effect of the management structure at freight yards on the deployment of innovations requires research.

The implementation of certain technologies to facilitate the automation of freight yards, such as automated coupling, may require rapid and complete deployment to avoid creating a dual system. The need to handle wagons in two different manners may undermine the advantages that could be obtained by incremental increases in the automation level.

The possibilities offered by automating other auxiliary processes performed in the HY have not been addressed in this thesis. These processes include customs clearance, repair of vehicles and inspection of specific goods.

More detailed research of the time savings, and therefore the economic advantages, of shunting automation should be performed. Simulation of different scenarios with suitable software (e.g. PLANIMATE, VILLON) may lead to more precise assessment.

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National projects

Project	Main topics (linked to automated shunting)	Leader	Time interval	Source
Galileo Go!	Develop a Galileo navigation receiver for railway applications	Institute of Automatic Control (RWTH Aachen)	04/2015 – 06/2018	[Galileo Online: GO! n.d.]
AuRa	Development of an autonomous vehicle for automation of internal shunting	G. Zwiehoff GmbH	09/2018 – 08/2021	[BMVI 2019:56]
ZBA 4.0	Automation of MY	DB Cargo	unknown	
Rang-E	Autonomous shunting in ports	Institute für Seeverkehrswirtschaft und Logistik	08/2017 – 07/2019	[ISL 2017:1]
RANGierASSistent	Development of a guiding system for secured shunting operations in MY	Institute for Production Systems (Bochum University)	unknown	[Franzen et al. 2017a]
EVI-POS	Wagon positioning	ECD Electronic Components GmbH	01/2017 – 06/2019	[BMVI 2019:56]
Güterwagen 4.0	Automated wagon	Lenord, Bauer & Co. GmbH Reuschling GmbH Fachhochschule Aachen	09/2018 – 08/2021	[BMVI 2019:56]
Innovative Güterwagen	Automated coupling; automated wagon; wagon positioning; wagon identification	DB Cargo VTG AG	10/2016 – 04/2019	[Innovativer Güterwagen 2019:2]
Ein-Personen-Betrieb	Automated coupling; automated brake test; anti-collision warning system	SBB Cargo	unknown	[SBB Cargo 2019]

5L-Zug	Innovative freight wagon; automated coupling; harvesting system	SBB Cargo	2016 - 2021	<i>[Sonntag 2017]</i>
Traxens	Wagon positioning; wagon identification; harvesting	Traxens	unknown	<i>[Dubey 2019]</i>

European projects (S2R IP5)

Project	Topics (linked to automated shunting)	Leader	Time interval	Source
Smart-Rail (Lighthouse)	Not directly related	TNO	05/2015 – 04/2018	[SMART RAIL n.d.]
FFL4E (CFM)	Not directly related	Bombardier	09/2016 – 05/2019	[FFL4E n.d.]
FR8RAIL (CFM)	Automated coupling Wagon telematics and electrification	Trafikverket	09/2016 – 08/2019	[FR8RAIL n.d.]
ARCC (CFM)	Automated brake test Real-time yard management	DB AG	09/2016 – 08/2019	[ARCC n.d.]
SMART (OC)	Autonomous obstacle detection Real-time MY management system	University of Bremen	10/2016 – 09/2019	[SMART n.d.a]
INNOWAG (OC)	Wagon identification Energy harvesting Data communication	University of Newcastle	11/2016 – 04/2019	[INNOWAG n.d.]
DYNAFREIGHT (OC)	No directly related	UNIFE	11/2016 – 06/2018	[DYNAFREIGHT n.d.]
FR8HUB (CFM)	Intelligent Video Gate	Trafikverket	09/2017 – 08/2020	[FR8HUB n.d.]
OptiYard (OC)	Real-time yard management	UIC	10/2017 – 09/2019	[OptiYard n.d.]
FR8RAIL II (CFM)	Automated coupling Wagon intelligence	Bombardier	05/2018 – 04/2021	[FR8RAIL II n.d.]
M2O (OC)	Not directly related	University of Rome Tor Vergata	12/2018 – 11/2020	[M2O n.d.]